

RISING QUEER HORIZONS AND INDIAN NATIONALISM

Manju Theresa Mathew

M.A Women and Gender Studies

University of North Carolina at Greensboro

Previous- M.A in International Relations, JNU, New Delhi

Delegation to the 2nd International Women's Rights Assembly
(Regd: 05IWRA2)

Abstract:

This paper is intended at throwing more focus and scope for queer theory in the postcolonial Indian context. The colonial period particularly the introduction of Section 377 in the Indian Penal Code had a huge impact on the way sexualities has been understood and expressed in our nation.. Through an analysis of the movie Fire as well as through the response to the movie the paper is trying to demonstrate some of the integral fights in the path towards sexual freedom and how domestic violence is always normalized and often validated as necessary to maintain a good and moral family.

Keywords: *Section 377, Domestic violence, Hindutva politics, Fire, LGBT, Postcolonial India*

The twenty-first century saw many dramatic historical events and one of the most important and still ongoing one is the queer movement and the cultural ripples it causes in many nations and societies. In this paper, I am tracing the beginnings of modern gay identities in the postcolonial Indian society and the repercussion's it caused as well as the challenges it faces. The precolonial India was a state with much less, heteronormativity due to a lot of historical aspects as well as the absence of strong influx of Christian morals which made monogamous marriage the accepted norm. Many South Indian Brahmanical (upper caste Hindu) traditions never followed monogamy as well as the Muslims. As Foucault argues Homosexuality as an identity is a modern construct and this idea is aptly applicable here. The forces that oppose gay rights in India are mainly the religious structures and they lack a proper understanding of the Indian culture or traditions prior to British intervention. In the name of preserving and

protecting the culture and values of India, they are merely protecting the cultural changes that colonialism brought in into India as a means of civilizing the Indian population. My attempt in this paper is to bring out this aspect analyzing the reactions to the movie *Fire*. The modern gay movement in the west has significantly impacted and fueled similar movements in the developing world. Hence this is a movement that is rising up asking for legitimate representation as well as acceptance as minority using the western homosexual identity. The organizations that oppose these groups are the conservative religious fanatic groups that are denying certain minorities their rights by invoking a false sense of culture and history.

Post-colonialism is the intellectual reaction to the western theories that is obsessed with race and class. Representing the nations which were under the colonial occupations, postcolonial theories have always tried to enlist different parameters to analyze societal

RISING QUEER HORIZONS AND INDIAN NATIONALISM

Manju Theresa Mathew

The Rights, Vol-III: Issue-I

8th, March, 2017

ISSN: 2454-9096 (online)

power structures that create oppression in the third world. Postcolonial studies thus developed in a context where the western theories proved adequate to understand the issues of postcolonial societies and hence offer unique solutions. The most important issue was that most western theories revolved around race and class. In the context of the third world, these two doesn't really apply. My focus in this paper is the Indian society, which is fundamentally caste ridden. A caste is a form of social stratification that is based on the jobs performed and the jobs are passed on generations. It is this caste structure that creates hierarchies of power and privilege. The influence colonialism had on this stratification and consequent oppression is also important. Thus the western theories on race and class do not offer much in the way of understanding these different social hierarchies and the power structures. Culture plays a crucial role here but the present rhetoric of culture is one modified by the colonial intervention and hence it doesn't really involve the ancient Indian cultural values. Analyzing queer movement hence involve a comprehensive understanding of a myriad of factors. My goal in the paper is to provide an overview of queer movement in India and the historic legacy, legal battles and analyze some factors that have contributed to this. Globalization has led to the consolidation of cultures across the globe. As Marx exclaimed the technological progress gets easily accepted but the cultural changes do not. This is very much visible in many developing countries post liberalization in the contemporary world. Citing family as the unit of preserving the culture and values the rights of many of these sexual minorities are denied and is seen as a bad influence from western culture while capitalism and its technological advancements are always hailed as great achievements of the human race worth implementing.

Modern Gay Identity

Modern gay identities and its spread towards becoming a global movement can be attributed to globalization. Two main theoretical standpoints on the gay identity is that of constructivists and essentialists. The essentialist argument is that homosexuality is not a new development but instead it has been there for centuries and the social constructivist drawing from Foucault posits that like heterosexuality homosexuality too is a social construction. Thus modern homosexuality has three main distinguishing features. Firstly, it distinguishes between sexual and gender transgression, secondly, there is an emphasis on emotional and sexual relationship and lastly development of public homosexual worlds (Howley page 26). Both constructivists, as well as the essentialist idea of sexuality, do not give a proper understanding when it comes to postcolonial societies. The rigid gender differentiation came to exist as a result of contact with western civilization. But there are some ancient texts which depict homosexuality. The issue here is that whether there was a sharp distinction between genders, and was homosexuality viewed in the same way as in modern societies is not clear. Thus there is no proper understanding or the foundations of on the history of sexuality in these societies. But considering the contemporary situation we can safely assume that the rise of gay movements is largely drawing its activism as well as history from the western movement and foundations of liberalism which advocate freedom of expression. Globalization and the transnational movements have contributed to this largely. In many parts of India, the defense against gay rights is from religious fundamentalist groups arguing that it is not part of Indian culture. These arguments definitely ignore the ancient cultural traditions and text and thus it is mainly the manifestation of colonial agenda that we see here. In many third world regions, the gender identities became rigid into the binary structure post involvement with the western incursions. Thus these forces against gay liberation are actually the

RISING QUEER HORIZONS AND INDIAN NATIONALISM

Manju Theresa Mathew

The Rights, Vol-III: Issue-I

8th, March, 2017

ISSN: 2454-9096 (online)

invisible extension of colonialism and its Biopolitics.

Political economy of Homosexuality

Homosexuality has come to denote an important aspect of modernity. It has now become a value that is to be promoted for people and societies to attain the ideals of political liberalism. I am very skeptical of the sharp divisions of gender in societies and also of western and non-western sexualities. Also, any discussion of gender and sexual identities cannot happen in a vacuum, it should always be analyzed in the context of larger socio-political as well as economic context.

In most of the postcolonial societies, it is mostly the influence and a said progress towards democratic ideals which has its roots in liberal ideology that gay rights stem from. It is interesting to note here that it was these western nations which adopted a liberal democratic model at the same time denied these rights to the colonies. This said I want to introduce the idea of neoliberalism and its role in political economy which resisted the spread of homosexuality for its need for profit was always structured around the institution of family. Since western societies had changed and adapted to gay families these corporations had already adapted and started producing consumer goods to gay families as well. This cultural shift manifested in the form of different media programs which normalized gay relationships and hence played a large role in 'uncloseting' many sexual minorities in developing countries. Most gay rights activism is centered around the idea of legalizing gay marriage in India which results in the making of imitation of heterosexual families and thus targets to market the capitalist products. Post world war II and decolonization the white supremacy took a different turn in the form of neo-liberalism and prominence of neoliberal institutions. Although many western countries legalized gay rights very

recently when it comes to the third world it is often portrayed that the cultural backwardness of these countries is what is preventing the legal triumph for gay pride. It is here that the western hegemonic structure can be seen and the moral value of liberalism marketed. The third world population becomes the subjects to sell this promoting a culture of consumerism in a way finding more markets to the capitalist production. In fact, the newest aspect of neocolonialism fashions its invisible hands through constructing the identity of homosexuality.

History

Many ancient Indian texts mention nonheterosexual intercourse. Hence homosexuality is not something new in the Indian culture. Ancient texts as well as many temple carvings show that homosexuality could have been an acceptable practice. Later Arthashastra an ancient treatise on statecraft mentions small punishments for homosexual acts. It was under the British Raj or the colonial government that banned all homosexual acts under section 377 of Indian Penal Code which still exists to present day.

Although the law exists there have been fewer convictions under homosexuality. In 2009, in an epic case, the Delhi High court decriminalized gay sex and section 377 was removed. But it was reversed in 2013 when the supreme court ruled against this Delhi high court decision. Political parties like Congress, Aam Aadmi support gay rights but other parties do not. This lack of political unity is one reason slowing the momentum in bringing gay rights. There have been many instances where homosexuals are discriminated and moral policing subjected them to violence. In 2012 during a hearing the Supreme Court viewed that homosexuality should be viewed in the light of changing social structures across the world. In a separate incident, the Union home minister opined that "this is highly immoral and against social order".

RISING QUEER HORIZONS AND INDIAN NATIONALISM

Manju Theresa Mathew

The Rights, Vol-III: Issue-I

8th, March, 2017

ISSN: 2454-9096 (online)

First gay pride march happened in 2008 in the cities of Delhi, Calcutta, and Bangalore. Thus most of the activism is mainly centered in the big cities, the main areas of globalization and dissipation of ideas. Thus it is mainly the urban elite which is powering these movements. Apart from the major cities, no other areas have a strong advocacy movement for the gay rights. These groups thus represent a minuscule population and in fact a minuscule gay/lesbian population. Same-sex marriage as of now is not legal and in many places same sex relations are shamed. Such situation once led to the suicide of a lesbian couple in the southern state of Kerala, since their families didn't approve of the relation.

Sexuality has been a subject silenced throughout history. As Michael Foucault in "*History of Sexuality*" concludes, talking about sexuality is the important feature of the modern century and a resistance to power structure's that silenced it. There are two important historical facts that brought sexuality and talking about it in the public arena in India. Firstly, the AIDS epidemic which made sex a topic to be discussed in public situations and secondly the media coverage due to liberalization policy of 1991 which widened tremendously television coverage and satellites and thus talking sex, became a common phenomenon. This could be the main reason why homosexuality was identified as part of the western culture by radical elements. Thus when movie *fire* was released the public had a good idea about the western notions of homosexuality and the radical elements in Indian culture were quick to call it anti-national.

Homo-sexuality in Exemplifying FIRE

Deepa Mehta, a Canadian- Indian directed this movie starring a prominent actor Shabana Azmi and a debutant Nandita Das. As both their husbands are indifferent to them, they finally share their miseries and fall in love. Azmi plays the role of a devout wife, Radha who until meeting Sita

(Nanditha Das) obediently manages the joint family. Sita is more of a free spirited person and has many rebellious remarks against the customs and traditions that often do not give women any choice. Immediately after reaching her husband's home the marriage Sita wears her husband's pants and imitates smoking which many youngsters in India considers to be cool and liberating. The film shows the expected role of a wife, many times Radha has to help her husband get over his desire by lying next to him. Since Radha can't conceive he considers sex to be redundant in their life, as the religious ascetic he is devoted to has preached that sex is only for procreation. Also, women are considered to be passive humans and should not possess desires. The only expectation from them is to be a dutiful wife. Sita's husband is in love with another girl who he thinks is modern and beautiful while he thinks Sita doesn't possess both qualities. Both these women are not desired by their husbands.

The movie shows the cultural and customary duties of what is expected from a wife, a view that is prevalent across the country. In this context *Fire* has two implications, firstly it disrupted the traditional family structure. When both Radha and Sita indulged in intimacy and later when they decided to leave. This also was a threat to the heterosexuality that is often seen as the natural order of relations. Secondly, it showed that women can have desires and their bodies although bound by traditional customs can break free. Unlike many women who suppress their desires Mehta's story unraveled a new identity for women hood and along with it the idea that these cultural norms are imaginary and changeable.

One of the most prominent gay protests came in response to the movie *fire*. The movie was based on a joint Indian family where two sister-in-law's fall in love. This revolutionary theme set in 1990 middle-class Delhi household was considered an unnatural theme by many right-wing political parties and hence led to nationwide protests

RISING QUEER HORIZONS AND INDIAN NATIONALISM

Manju Theresa Mathew

The Rights, Vol-III: Issue-I

8th, March, 2017

ISSN: 2454-9096 (online)

and violence. Many theaters were vandalized and RSS, a right wing party proclaimed that homosexuality is not part of Indian Culture. To make sure to brand *Fire* as an abomination many of these parties resorted to old fashioned 'goonda' violence. The sequels to fire, the *earth* and *water* also met similar fate. There are two aspects of this protest against the movie one is the fight against globalization and secondly what Indian women should be and how they should behave.

Globalization is very much associated with neo-liberalism and its trade and commerce strategies. Although trade and commerce have been happening all throughout history it is the technological and media revolution that marks the present globalization different. Thus globalization is a process that is happening from the technologically superior west to the not so advanced developing world. In most of these developing countries all technological and economic advancement according to the western lines is favored but not cultural change. And women's bodies have been a territory where violent resistance against this cultural change has happened. Women celebrating Valentine's day or going to pubs have faced serious physical violence by the right wing political parties. Women's bodies transfers to the embodiment of culture in this Hindutva politics and such violence is tolerated in the name of protecting culture. Some assumptions made by the protagonists of this violence is women in India is defined as the 'Hindu women' neglecting the fact that there are many Christian, Jew, Muslim and even a large number of different ethnicities and tribal women in the country. This narrow view is then conditioned by the idea that women should be devoted loyal subjects to their husbands. Thus women who choose to be independent and decide their lives become a threat to the so defined Indian culture. As a country that was under colonial rule for centuries, this violent reaction to globalization and western culture can be to an extent a defense against any form of

future colonial power. But this rhetoric is blinded by the fact that they are using a narrow idea of Indian society and culture. Also, this neo right wing agenda is against human rights as well as against democratic liberal ideals.

Sudha Chauri of 'Mahila Aghadi' the right wing organization which launched the first fight against the movie explained the act saying that "The film is against the very structure of our society, this behavior is totally unnatural and bad." Meena Kulkarni of the Shiv Sena agreed to this, adding that "Azmi (the actor in *Fire*) has insulted Indian women...even if such things go on the sly, by showing them on the screen we are actually informing others about such acts of perversion. If women's physical needs get fulfilled through lesbian acts, the institution of marriage will collapse, and reproduction of human beings will stop". Uma Bharati, a member of the BJP (another right wing Hindu fundamentalist party) Government, accused Deepa Mehta of 'pervert thinking' and denied that lesbianism existed in India.

The women in *Fire* showed the important revolution of walking away from Family. A plot where traditionally violence against women has been happening such as Sati, child marriage, dowry etc. These characters of Sita and Radha defied all these and went to the extent of leaving their families. This was the second most important contestation Hindu groups had with the movie. From the subtle and devoted wives that they should be, they decided to break the family ties and their marriage and hence leave their husbands for the sake of their love. The movie broke the traditional family which is the basic foundation in the Hindutva definition of Indian culture and posed the threat of ideal Indian women.

The next criticism towards the movie was that of the problem of representation. Madhu Kishawar, the editor of a progressive women's magazine *Manushi* argued that Canada based Deepa Mehta being an

outsider is not capable of representing Indian women. According to Kishawar, if anything Fire only increases the western stereotypical notions of Indian women and thus a failure to portray the real Indian women. This is not entirely true as in the light of human rights and obviously the question of choice the story aptly brings out the way women are treated in a joint family. When culture and traditions become enforced it is not arguable that in such societies women are liberated and enforce their choices. The film also brings out some complex issues facing the queer movement, for example, Sita remarks that there is no word in our language to denote our relation.

One issue with the movie is that it shows the relation between Radha and Sita as an imitation of heterosexual relation. I am noting two scenes here first when they both dance together, Radha dress up in the traditional Saree and Sita in her husband's Shirts and Pants. Secondly, where Radha gives Sita mint and says that Brides are supposed to have a fresh breath, indicating marriage as a subtle reference to their relation.

Mehta brings in the erotic homosexual images through otherwise homosocial activities like oiling the hair, messaging feet etc. Many of these female bonding plots were largely absent from Indian cinema before. Also to the unsuspecting audience of their husbands see these acts as normal and they consider them to be fortunate to have such a good family. These images of otherwise considered innocent acts portrayed in an erotic way also disrupt the family structure and the established forms of relations in the family. The Fire was the first movie to portray homosexuality in the domestic setting and since then many movies followed such as Dostana where a gay couple kissing was portrayed on screen and the Censor board or any organization didn't organize a protest. Fire, in turn, created a coming out process for the film industry and

also to an extent made homosexuality an acceptable plot in movies.

Spivak's question of "Can the subaltern speak?" is to a large extent answered in this movie. By placing the female characters in the subaltern setting and eventually turning the story to them taking hold of their bodies and desires points to the fact that the subaltern can speak. "In addition, Nair and Mehta's female characters are constructed as Indian women with agency and not simply as ideological constructs of nationalism" (Moodley page 68). Indian nationalism has always revolved around the idea of purity of its women as chaste and obedient and ascribing these values to the motherland. These values later take the form of the obedient wife whose only role is to produce sons for the valor of the nation. It is the cultural enforcement of this idea that is the main discriminating force in many Indian societies that prevents women from owning their bodies or become bodies with desire. "Anything that threatens this image of Indian women is a betrayal of culture, god, nation, family and the moral structure" (Bhattacharjee page 172).

Breaking these stereotypes is the most emotional part of the movie. A strong Sita walks away from the house and a conflicted Radha is reluctant to leave at first as she decides to talk to her husband before leaving. But she changes her mind by reclaiming her body and sexuality which was earlier bound by customs and traditional norms. Culture and traditions when it becomes something enforced upon, women's bodies become subjects where oppression is instilled. The film provided a plot to break away and decide your destiny. From the place of oppression and subjugation, these bodies transform to sites of resistance and later into liberated forms. Unlike the western view of third world women as oppressed and dependent, these women show a different identity and is willing to leave their husbands and make a living of their own. Hence the movie successfully breaks the western

RISING QUEER HORIZONS AND INDIAN NATIONALISM

Manju Theresa Mathew

The Rights, Vol-III: Issue-I

8th, March, 2017

ISSN: 2454-9096 (online)

stereotype of third world women too. Also, these movies created a space for resistance against colonial and nationalistic construction of Indian women and paved a way of redefining the Indian women, identity as well as their desire.

Nationalism and queer identities

The present Hindu rhetoric of nationality excludes many rights to women, transgender, gay and lesbian communities. Along the process of anti-colonial freedom movement developed the Hindu patriotic groups and the partition of India and Pakistan created a hard religious divide in the society which has its origins in the colonial government. Divide and rule based on religious differences were a strategic policy the British implemented to keep the Indian uprising in check. The cultural hegemony that Christianity had during colonization era influenced Indian society. The indigenous Christian communities were converted forcefully to Catholics under Portuguese, Dutch and later British rule. The missionaries that came along characterized Indian culture as Barbaric and hence a Christianization of the society underwent. "The flawed promises of nationalism as an all-inclusive, horizontal community are especially visible from the positions of women and marginalized groups" (Puri, page 137). Considering the fact that Transgender was identified as the third gender only in 2014 and the legal provisions for their wellbeing are still in development mode along with the lack of gay rights the state definitely does not consider these groups as real citizens as heterosexual people. States are, in other words, "powerful sites" of symbolic and cultural production rather than simply bureaucratic apparatuses that are natural or linear structures with power and authority flowing upward (Ferguson and Gupta 2002). Hence during the formation of state identity during freedom struggle the citizenship mainly went to the heterosexual population as organized under the British rule and the rest of the population was left behind. The

consolidation of Indian population into male and female categories came under the colonial rule. The same model was adopted post-independence. Being a Hindu majority state the Hindu ideals took a precedent over others. To understand more about the particular brand of Hindu nationalism that is propagated now, it has its origins in the freedom struggle and was cultivated as hatred for the colonial empire, of Muslims and other non-Hindu identities and adopted the colonial Christian moral values of family and sexuality. All Hindu right-wing activists see the queer movement as a moral decay and erosion of Indian culture and aping the western particularly US culture and participating in the cultural imperialism of the west. With the liberalization of 1990s the family became the crucial site where aspirations and apprehensions unleashed by the forces of globalization were negotiated (Ghosh in handbook of gender. Page 429).

The family is the center of all these debates and the main goal is to preserve the stereotype of north Indian Hindu joint family system which is often equated as the symbol of Indian cultural values and traditions. Numerous movies and television soaps that were released during the liberalization era clearly shows the anxieties that were faced and the feeling that joint family system will soon disintegrate into nuclear families. Obedience to elders or the head of the family who is normally a male member is the norm that gives you blessings from gods to a long prosperous life. Dissidents from this way of living are always portrayed as falling into trouble and later repent and the families welcome the changed and transformed person into their lives. Thus globalization set in motion a lot of cultural anxieties in motion although everyone welcomed the economic gains wholeheartedly. Changing lifestyles, as well as the changing romantic relationships took the control over desire and relationships from families to individuals. This is the biggest struggle that manifests in the form of right-wing political actions to preserve the

RISING QUEER HORIZONS AND INDIAN NATIONALISM

Manju Theresa Mathew

The Rights, Vol-III: Issue-I

8th, March, 2017

ISSN: 2454-9096 (online)

culture of India and its great heritage. There have been subtle media portrayals of homosexuality but most of it took the form of confused friendship or cross-dressing. There are many female characters who loves dressing like men and eventually when they come of marriageable age they often transform to the stereotype of Indian women, emphasizing the importance of following the cultural and moral values and preparing yourself for the blissful married life. Thus the queer movement requires building more on the historical aspects of sexuality and its evolution in India to counter the anti-imperial sentiments that is unleashed against rights of queer movement.

Conclusion

Quoting Neville Hoad "In the moment of writing, the emergence of an international public sphere dedicated to finding and making "homosexuals" in parts of the world that have not seen public articulations of such persons may further allow "homosexuality" to be seen as an ongoing imperial project." This statement is particularly apt in the Indian context. The rise of transnational gay rights movement has made one category of othering possible through the use of homosexuality. A strategy to mark national and cultural differences in the population. Such a standpoint fails to recognize the regimes of power and intimate systems of regulation that promote heterosexuality as a political-economic necessity, not only subjugating women in the process but also obliterating socially legitimate space for sexual alterity. The choice is not really the problem, and as such, feminist and lesbian causes are intimately symbiotic, meaning that lesbian subjects must be at the heart of responses to masculine domination (Menon, 2005). The current queer movement thus is multifaceted and is a response to oppressive family and control of sexuality and the institutions and structures that propagate this. It has self-liberation at its core. It is also a reaction to hegemonic power that caste system in Hindu

culture create sand which has created historic oppression over centuries. Many writers see the gay pride parade that happened recently as the cultural revolution that was long blooming. The rhetoric of anti-nationalism against gay rights is a misguided as well anti-democratic and legalizing gay rights is long due in Indian culture.

Works Cited

- Ghosh, Shohini. "Forbidden love and passionate denials" in Ray, Raka. Handbook of Gender. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012. Print.
- Boyce, Paul. "Truths and (mis)representations: Adrienne Rich, Michel Foucault and Sexual Subjectivities in India." *Sexualities*. 11 (2008): 1-2. Print.
- Chatterjee, Nandini. *The Making of Indian Secularism: Empire, Law and Christianity, 1830-1960*. Basingstoke, Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan, 2011. Print.
- Ferguson, Roderick and Kyungwon, Grace. "The Sexual and Racial Contradictions of Neoliberalism". *Journal of Homosexuality* (2012): Pages 1057-1063. Online.
- Ghosh, Shohini. *Queer Film Classics : Fire : A Queer Film Classic*. Vancouver, US: Arsenal Pulp Press, 2010. ProQuest ebrary. Web. 8 November 2016.
- Hoad, Neville. *African Intimacies : Race, Homosexuality, and Globalization*. Minneapolis, US: University of Minnesota Press, 2006. ProQuest ebrary. Web. 19 November 2016.
- Kim-Puri, H. "Conceptualizing Gender-Sexuality-State-Nation." *Gender & Society*. 19.2 (2005): 137-159. Print.
- Marsh, Julie and Brasted, Howard. "Fire, the BJP and Moral Society." *Journal of South Asian studies* (2007): Pages 235-24. Print.
- Menon, N. (2005) 'How Natural is Normal? Feminism and Compulsory Heterosexuality', in A. Narrain and G. Bhan (eds) *Because I Have a Voice: Queer Politics in India*. New Delhi: Yoda Press.
- Raj, Selva J, and Corinne G. Dempsey. *Popular Christianity in India: Riting between the Lines*. Albany: State University of New York Press, 2002. Internet resource.
- SubsheniMoodley *Masters in Culture, Communication and Media Studies* (2003) Postcolonial feminisms speaking through an 'accented' cinema: the construction of Indian women in the films of Mira Nair and Deepa Mehta, *Agenda*, 17:58, 66-75

PARENTAL ROLE IN IMPARTING SEX EDUCATION TO ADOLESCENT GIRLS IN NOIDA

Hrishika

(1st Author) Phd Scholar, Amity Institute of Social Science,
Dr. Shradha Sharma (2nd Author) and Phd Guide
Asst. Professor in Amity Institute of Social Sciences
Amity University, Noida, UP, INDIA

Delegation to the 2nd International Women's Rights Assembly
(Regd: **08IWRA2**)

Abstract:

Sex education is information about sex beliefs and attitudes. Sex education helps us to understand the concepts of sexual identity, sexual relationship, intimacy and consequences of poor knowledge of sexuality. Parents are the first teachers to children; their primary duty is to socialize and maintain healthy communication. Adolescent is the crucial age and if proper guidance and knowledge are not provided it could lead to negative consequences. The present study focuses on the role of parents in providing sex education to adolescent girls in Noida. The objectives of the study are to understand the role of parents in providing sex education, to understand the importance of sex education among adolescent girls and to identify the consequences among adolescent in the lack of sex education. The data is collected using self made questionnaires for adolescent girls and parents (interviewed separately) with 60 sample size (30 adolescent girls and 30 parents) in Noida. The data collected is computed in excel sheet with tables and diagrams.

Keywords: *Adolescent girls, Adolescent problems, Importance of sex education, Parents, Sex education*

Sex education is information about sex beliefs and attitudes. Sex education helps us to understand the concepts of sexual identity, sexual relationship, intimacy as well as the consequences of poor knowledge of sexuality. The main objective of sex education is to aware children, adolescence and young people about their sexuality and sexual roles and responsibilities. In Indian society sex is considered as a very sensitive subject to discuss openly among family members or within society. The United Nations define adolescents as individuals being 10-19 years

old.¹ Adolescent is the crucial age and if proper guidance and knowledge are not provided it could lead to negative consequences. According to Adolescence Education Programme 2010 (NCERT) adolescence is popularly understood as a phase in the teenage years of the life of a human being. It is a period of transition between childhood and adulthood: its distinctiveness is reflected in rapid

¹ UNICEF (2011), "The State of the World's Children – Adolescence: An age of opportunity", New York. P. 16. Retrieved from: http://www.unicef.org/sowc2011/pdfs/SOWC-2011-Main-Report_EN_02092011.pdf

biological, cognitive and socio-emotional changes.

Role of parents in imparting sex education to adolescent girls: Parents are the first and primary source of knowledge to their children; their primary duty is to rear and socialize them. The main element of parent-adolescent relationship should be based on healthy communication. Parents, likely the most consistent influence in children's lives, are in a unique position to influence young people's health and personal development, and their transition to sexual life (World Health Organization, 2007). In India, notwithstanding the recognition in policies and programmes of the need to actively engage parents in enabling adolescents to make safe and healthy transitions to adulthood (Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, 2006), evidence about parent-child interaction and communication, particularly with regard to sensitive matters such as the physical changes associated with puberty, sex, pregnancy and sexually transmitted infections/ HIV is sparse².

Negative consequences of poor sex knowledge: Sex education is important for each and every adolescent without proper knowledge on sex education adolescent girls can witness a number of problems which could harm their self-confidence. There is ample number of researches which shows the consequences of poor sex knowledge. The negative consequences in the lack of sex education among adolescent girls are as follows:

- **Risk of teen pregnancy/ child pregnancy:** If the proper guidance is not provided to adolescent girls at the right time it may result into teen pregnancy. During adolescent stage physical attraction towards opposite

sex is normal and due to which they may develop unhealthy physical relationships. Their regular sexual activeness can lead to the negative impact of unwanted pregnancy and risk of HIV/ AIDS and Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STD).

- **Child abandonment:** Researches has shown that unwanted pregnancy during adolescent period and before marriage is one of the major causes of child abandonment. Out of the societal pressure and lack of parental support these adolescent girls abandoned their new born babies which may lead to baby death and if the child survives he/she has to go through severe trauma of being rejected from the biological mother. Getnet Tedele had conducted a study in 2000 in Ethopihia. In the study "Child Abandonment: Five dramatic cases of mothers in Addis Ababa (Ethopihia)"; in the study he described five case studies of the mothers who abandoned their new born babies which resulted to the death of infants. The study was based on the direct interviews with the mothers who were in prison. The result of the study shown that young people are more likely to get involved in premarital sex and other risky behavior which exposes the possibility of future child abandonment.
- **Poor health condition:** Adolescent girls can confront diseases such as Sexually Transmitted Disease and also the risk HIV/AIDS in the absence of knowledge on sex related doubts. Also teen pregnancy can negatively impact the health of the girl who gives birth at the young age and it would further affect the baby's health.
- **Poor academic performance:** In the lack of sex education an adolescent girl can suffer shame at school and college which would hamper her

² M. Svodziva, F.Kurete, L. Ndlovu (2016). Parental Knowledge, Attitude and Perceptions towards Adolescent Sexual Reproductive Health in Bulawayo. International Journal of Humanities Social Sciences and Education Vol. 3 (4) PP 62-71

education and academic performance.

- **Emotional distress:** Due to lack of sex education an adolescent girl can indulge into unaccepted social behaviors and can face psychological and emotional effects like feeling of shame, shock, confusion, fear, guilt, grief, distrust, loneliness, anger, lack of confidence, attachment difficulties, poor peer relation, self-injurious behaviors (e.g. suicide attempts).
- **Social un-acceptance:** Adolescents who are sexually active and become pregnant they face rejection and are highly unaccepted by the society. Their parents and families also don't support them because of the societal pressure. In Indian society pre marital sex is not acceptable.
- **Economical issues:** Also the teen suffers economically due to lack of support from parents and society as a result they are not able to sustain.

I. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the present study are-

1. To understand the role of parents in providing sex education to their adolescent girls
2. To understand the importance of sex education among adolescent girls
3. To identify the consequences among adolescent girls in the lack of sex education.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present research study is an attempt to examine the role of parents in providing sex education to their adolescent girls and to understand the importance of sex education for adolescence girls. The descriptive research design was adopted for the study.

The nature of the study is quantitative. The data is computed in excel sheet.

Purposive and snow ball sampling techniques were adopted to collect data. The total sample size is 60; out of which 30 adolescent girls and 30 parents both mother and father (parents as one unit) were interviewed. The sample universe is Noida. Adolescent girls were approached at their respective schools/ colleges in Noida to participate in the survey. Parents were interviewed at their residents in Noida to collect data.

The data is collected using structured interview schedule and interview method. The data is collected using two sets of questionnaires having closed ended questions. The questionnaires are-

- 1) Sex education survey for adolescent girls and,
- 2) Sex education survey for parents.

The topics which are covered on sex education in the questionnaire particularly focusing on- pre marital relationship, openness of adolescent girls with their parents, parental view on providing sex education to their adolescent girls, use of contraceptives in order to prevent teenage pregnancy and diseases and knowledge on consequences of poor sex knowledge.

III. MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The present study is an attempt to understand the role of parents in providing sex education to their adolescent girls as well as to examine the views of adolescent girls on the same. The outcome of the study is categorized into two sections: findings from the parents of adolescent girls and findings from the adolescent girls.

Parents view towards imparting sex education to their adolescent girls:

40% parents who have adolescent girls from the age group of 13-15 years and 30% parents who have adolescent girls from the age group of 16-18 years participated actively in the survey.

All respondents (30) agree that their adolescent daughter share their problems regularly with them. They reported that their daughters do share issues related with their academics, friends and about their doubts on sex. All parents also agree that their daughters should share their sex related concerns with them. However 47% of parents reported that their daughters only share doubts related to physical changes with them. Their daughters do not discuss about their doubts on sex, sexual intimacy, sexual reproduction and contraceptives. They also reported that they have never initiated such talks with their adolescent daughters.

All parents do not agree with the idea of pre marital sex and they have never discussed with their daughters on this issue. However 30% parents reported that they have given the information on birth control/ contraceptives with their daughters when they asked so. 70% parents have never discussed or shared the information on birth control/ contraceptives with them. They believe that their daughters must be aware of it as they watch commercial advertisements in television but they have not spoken to their daughters openly on the matter.

70% of parents have never discussed about the risk of HIV/STD and pregnancy with their daughters. They reported that their daughters are attending schools/ colleges and they will learn about it from their teachers.

The majority 70% of parents reported that they have never discussed about abstinence (avoid sexual activities) with their daughters. Only 20% parents have shared the information with their adolescent daughters and rest 10% didn't answer.

Adolescent girls view on importance of sex education and their communication with their parents:

60% of adolescent girls are from the age group of 19 years and above and 20% from the age group of 16-18 years participated actively in the survey. Only 6.67% adolescent girls from the age group of 10-12 years and 13.33% from the age group of 13-15 years turned up for the interview. All respondents (30) are aware of sex. The majority 73.3% know about sex through their friends or through internet and only 16.7% know about sex through their parents. The source of getting information is not reliable and accurate.

The majority of adolescent girls 83.33% discuss their problems with their parents. 56.67% adolescent girls reported that the issues which they share with their parents are related to academics/ school and college.

60% of the adolescent girls agree that one should share sex related concerns with their parents and 40% were confused about sharing with the parents. However only 23.33% adolescent girls share their sex related concern with their parents. These girls reported that they are close to their mothers and never discuss about it with their fathers and brothers.

73.33% adolescent girls reported that they do not share their sex related issues and problems with their parents because they prefer to discuss with their friends/ siblings and they feel hesitated in sharing with their parents. The data shows the lack of communication between parents and adolescent girls over the issue.

Only 30% of the adolescent girls agree with the idea of pre-marital sex and 70% did not agree or denied to answer. Those who were agreed prefer use of condoms for safe sex and they learn about using condoms from their friends.

70% of adolescent girls have information about birth control/contraceptives. 50% of adolescent girls know the use of condoms/contraceptives as a means of reducing the risk of HIV/AIDS and pregnancy and 50% of adolescent girls are not aware of it. The majority 56.67% of adolescent girls reported that their parents have never discussed about abstinence (avoid sexual activities) to avoid pregnancy and STD.

IV. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Sex education from parents and within the family environment is the need of the hour. The above mentioned data indicates that in spite of understanding the consequences of poor knowledge on sex related issues the majority of parents do not take initiative to talk to their adolescent girls. Similarly, in the case of adolescent girls, they prefer to talk to their friends and try to gather information from sources like books, movies and internet which are not dependable. This step may indulge them into risk. Adolescent girls also reported that they feel hesitated to discuss their concerns particularly related to sexual intimacy with their parents. They further shared that their parents are not open hence they have never shared such things with them. The healthy communication among parent-child is highly needed and should be initiated which is possible by creating a familiar environment at home. Parents should know the developmental changes during adolescent period. Educative programmes should be initiated by the government to teach parents about developmental issues and phases of their children. Parents should learn that discussion on sex will not lead their adolescent girls to involve in sexual activities. Parents who discuss about sex related doubts with their adolescence girls have suggested that all parents must discuss every issues including sex openly with their children, they should listen their problems and should earn the confidence of the child. They also suggested

sharing information with the boys as well. It was also found that parents consider that the major responsibility of providing sex education is of schools/ colleges and as a result they don't take initiative to talk to their adolescent girls. The results of the study indicating the role of the mother is paramount because mostly adolescent girls share these concerns with them and do not share such information with their fathers. Fathers should also initiate communication with their daughters on sex education. Sex education is not limited to discussion on physical changes and relationships which most of the parent-adolescent girls share with each others. Other issues like premarital sex, use of contraceptives/condoms, risk of HIV and STD etc should be discussed among them to help adolescence in building their self confidence and to remove their doubts related to their sexuality.

References:

1. Children – Adolescence: An age of opportunity”, New York. P. 16. Retrieved from: http://www.unicef.org/sowc2011/pdfs/SOWC-2011-Main-Report_EN_02092011.pdf UNICEF (2011), “The State of the World’s
2. Tadele Getnet (2000). “Child Abandonment: Five dramatic cases of mothers in Addis Ababa (Ethiopia)”
3. Mahajan P and Sharma N (2005). Parents attitude towards imparting sex education to their adolescent girls. *Anthropologist*, Volume 7(3): pp 197-199
4. M. Svodziva, F.Kurete, L. Ndlovu (2016). Parental Knowledge, Attitude and Perceptions towards Adolescent Sexual Reproductive Health in Bulawayo. *International Journal of Humanities Social Sciences and Education* Vol. 3 (4) PP 62-71
5. Saha Shelly (2000). Adolescent and their Need of the Sex Education. Published in *Health for the Millions*, pp 10-12
6. Study on Child Abuse: India 2007. Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India.

LIFE SKILLS INTERVENTION FOR URBAN AND RURAL ADOLESCENT GIRLS STAYING WITH ALCOHOLIC PARENTS IN SHILLONG

Lindsay Murray MSangma

(1st Author) Phd Scholar, Amity Institute of Social Sciences

Prof. Dr. Nirupama Prakash (2nd Author)

Director & Head of Amity Institute of Social Sciences,
Amity University, Noida, UP, India

Delegation to the 2nd International Women's Rights Assembly
(Regd: 09IWRA2)

Abstract:

The present Study focuses on Life Skills Intervention for Urban and Rural Adolescent Girls staying with Alcoholic Parents. The sample of the study consisted of 194 female adolescent's participants between the age group of 10-19 years from Shillong, Meghalaya, India. The Objective of the study were, to study the demographic profile of the adolescent girls, to provide life skills programme for the female adolescents, to compare the differences between urban and rural female adolescents by assessing life skills before and after intervention. The tools used were demographic profile, Children of Alcoholics Screening Test (CAST), (Pilat & Jones, 1985), Life Skills Assessment Scale (LSAS), (Nair, Subasree & Ranjan, 2010). The hypothesis was **H₀**: There will be significant differences between urban and rural female adolescents on the basis of life skill intervention **H₁**: There will be no significant differences between urban and rural female adolescents on the basis of life skill intervention. Purposive sampling was applied using structured and standardized questionnaire. The researcher has selected a descriptive research design in phase 1 and in phase 11 pre experimental research design was used. Only single group was included that is experimental group and control group was not included, single group was pretested and then exposed to the intervention programme and later again the experimental group was post tested. The collected data were computed and analysed using SPSS. The present study focuses on providing Life skills programme in the form of intervention to adolescents living with alcoholic parents

Keywords: *Life Skills Intervention, Urban, Rural, Adolescent Girls, Alcoholic Parents*

Adolescence as given by World Health Organisation the age group of 10-19 years, this age group requires special attention and proper guidance as the process of growing up is a critical stage for adolescents. Adolescence period can be viewed as stressful with growth and changing environment, some of the major stress factors often comes from school, family, peer pressure and their personal lives. Alcohol affects each member of the family

from the unborn child to alcoholic's spouse, which results not only physical problems for the alcoholics, but also may result in physical and psychological problems for other members of the family. Alcoholism is not simply an individual problem. Families often play a significant role in the cause and cure of alcohol problems. There are many highs and lows problems that go with it when someone is living with an alcoholic. Spouses and children are affected indirectly; the

effects can vary from being withdrawn to being enablers. (The American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry (AACAP), 2011) stated that children of alcoholics are four more times more likely than other children to become alcoholics themselves. Children of alcoholics develop poor self-image; have difficulties in school and establishing relationships with friends and teachers. Children are more at risk to child abuse, neglect and behavioural problems. Raj et.al (2012) conducted a comparative study on behavioral problems in children of alcohol dependent parents. Total sample was 60 children age ranged from 4-18 years, experimental and control group was compared. The results showed that high externalizing problems in children of alcohol dependent was found with regards to rule breaking behavior and aggressive behavior. Internalizing behavior was also higher among children of alcohol dependent. Behavioral problems, attention problems, poverty, lack of proper education, social problems, decreased parental monitoring, stress, lack of stimulation in the rearing environment were seen significantly higher in children of alcohol dependent as compared to control group. Stanley & Vanitha (2008) conducted a study on psychosocial correlates in adolescent children of alcoholics to see their adjustment and self-esteem. 50 children of alcoholics were taken and tools used were Self-esteem Index and Adjustment inventory. The result revealed that the majority of children of alcoholic manifest lower self-esteem and their adjustment were poor when compared with children of non-alcoholic. Anda et.al (2002), explored a study on those children's who are living with alcoholic parents, and main intension was to know about their childhood experience and whether living with alcoholic parents can have any adverse effect on the children like depression and alcoholism at later stage. Sample size comprised of 9346 adults where 20% of respondents reported having parental alcohol abuse and higher risk of adverse childhood problems. The result also

confirmed that children living with alcoholic parents experiences more problems like physical abuse, emotional abuse, sexual abuse, parental separation or divorce, adult children reported having higher depression risk and adverse childhood experiences develops low self-esteem, anxiety and difficulties in maintaining relationships.

The Purpose of selecting this topic is to understand the problems experienced by the adolescents staying with alcoholic parents and identify other factors which give birth to major problems and how the problems can affect the adolescents in their day to day life. The problems faced by the children of alcoholics are given less importance especially viewed in Indian Scenario. Children of alcoholic are at risk and deserve more attention in prevention and early intervention of problems. The present study focuses on providing Life skills programme in the form of intervention to adolescents girls living with alcoholic parents.

Methods

Objectives

To study the demographic profile of the adolescent girls

To provide life skills programme for the female adolescents

To compare urban and rural female adolescents by assessing life skills intervention

Hypothesis

Ho: There will be significant differences between female adolescents on the basis of life skill intervention **H₁:** There will be no significant differences among female adolescents on the basis of life skill intervention.

Sampling Method

The Universe of this Study includes the Urban and Rural Adolescents from Shillong, who fall under the age group of 10 to 19 years. The sample size for this Study consists of 194 participants who met the inclusion criteria for the study. The sample for the study was collected from adolescents who are studying in classes 6th, 7th, 8th, 9th and 10th. Purposive sampling design was selected based on the knowledge of a population and for the purpose of the study. The life skills intervention programme was conducted between the months of August to November, 2015, for urban area and for rural area in the months of May to July, 2016 in 15 sessions with 54 activities. Each session was activity based and participatory in nature. The major techniques used to impart information were games, drawing, sharing, brainstorming, group work, group discussion, story analysis, role play, presentation, discussion and lectures. A pre-test and post-test design was used with only experimental group and no control group to assess the life skills intervention programme. The researcher has selected a descriptive research design in phase I as the design is helpful to identify the demographic characteristics of the participants and in phase II pre experimental research design was used. Only single group was included that is experimental group and control group was not included, single group was pretested and then exposed to the intervention programme and later again the experimental group was post tested. The collected data were coded, classified and analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) 17.0 version. The obtained data were analyzed using descriptive statistics like frequency and percentage, mean and standard deviation, and Parametric test like Paired t-test.

Life Skills Intervention Programme

Programme was developed for the adolescents from August to November, 2015, for urban area and for rural area in the months of May to July, 2016 in 15 sessions with 54 activities, where the adolescents were engaged in active training and learning process through series of activities on the ten core life skills. The purpose of the programme is to make them aware of the ten core life skills, provide knowledge, information which then can help the adolescents develop positive thinking, healthy ways of living, promote their mental well-being and competencies to face the daily situations

Procedure

The data collection began with the researcher obtaining permission from the De-Addiction centers and seven different schools from Shillong, and when the permission was granted the researcher met each participant individually, explained about the research and gave them the copies of questionnaires. Researcher began with a brief introduction about the whole study prior to signing of the informed consent form. Pre- Assessment started after the responses from respondents and their positive feedback which started from last week of August for screening test to screen out children who are either living with or have lived with alcoholic parents along with socio demographic and standardized questionnaires were given. After analysis of the screening data, Phase II-Pre Assessment the participants were taken as experimental group was then exposed to intervention programme which started from first week of September till last week of October. From 1st week of November till last week of November was Phase III-Post Assessment, where the same sets of questionnaires were given to the participants and collected after one month. The Same procedure was also followed for rural area in the months of May to July,

2016. The researcher requested them to answer all the questions and respond spontaneously. The Head of the Department was requested to return the Questionnaire duly filled in within by students.

DESCRIPTION OF ASSESSMENT TOOLS

1. Demographic data sheet

The demographic data sheet consists of name, age, gender, education qualification, family type, parent's occupation, caste, religion and name of the school.

2. Children of Alcoholics Screening Test (CAST)

Children of Alcoholics Screening Test (CAST) (Pilat & Jones, 1985) are 30-item screening instrument developed to identify children who are either living with or have lived with alcoholic parents. The questions measure children's feelings, attitudes, perceptions, and experiences related to their

parents' drinking behaviour (Larson & Thayne, 1998; Pilat & Jones, 1985). Answering "yes" to six or more questions is the recommended threshold for identifying people as children of alcoholics (Pilat & Jones, 1985). The CAST has been shown to be both a valid and reliable measure, with a validity coefficient of .78 and a reliability coefficient of .98 (Pilat & Jones, 1985).

3. Life Skills Assessment Scale (LSAS)

Life Skills Assessment Scale (LSAS), scale can be administered to a group or to an individual (Nair, Subasree & Ranjan, 2010). LSAS consists of 100 items in the form of statements in-built with a 5-point scale for the respondent to check the appropriate response which is most descriptive of him/her. It has both positive and negative items. LSAS measures ten (10) dimensions of Life Skills. Reliabilities for the 100 indicators of LSAS as a whole were found to be split-half 0.82, test-retest 0.91 and Cronbach's Alpha 0.84 which was highly reliable and 89% concurrence.

Results and Discussion

Table: 1.1.1

Title: Demographic profile of the participants

Personal profile	Variable	Frequency	Percentage	Personal profile	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
1.Age	12-13	30	15.4	3.Family Type	Joint Family	53	27.3
	14-15	114	58.8		Nuclear Family	141	72.7
	16-18	50	25.8				
2.Education Qualification	Class 10	34	17.5	5. Caste	Schedule Tribe	112	57.7
	Class 9	85	43.8		General	27	13.9
	Class 8	38	19.6		Other	30	15.5
	Class 7	29	14.9		Backward Classes		
	Class 6	8	4.2		Schedule Caste	25	12.9

LIFE SKILLS INTERVENTION FOR URBAN AND RURAL ADOLESCENT GIRLS STAYING WITH ALCOHOLIC PARENTS IN SHILLONG

Lindsay Murray MSangma

The Rights, Vol-III: Issue-I

8th, March, 2017

ISSN: 2454-9096 (online)

6. Parent's Occupation	Government	32	16.5	8. Geographical Area	Urban	85	43.8
	Employee	7	3.6				
	Accountant	7	3.6				
	Banker	35	18				
	Business Man	32	16.5				
	Daily Labour	22	11.4				
	Shopkeeper	25	12.9				
	Social Worker	3	1.5				
	Freelancer	21	10.8				
	Farmer	10	5.2				
	Fisherman						
	7. Religion	Christian	113				
Hindu		55	28.4				
Muslim		26	13.4				

The above table 1.1.1 presents the distribution of participants in relation to personal information that is age, Gender, educational qualification, family type, parent's occupation, caste and religion. Based on the above table it is evident that out of 194 participants, 114(58.8%) participants belongs to the age group of 14-15 years, 85(43.8%) participants are studying in class 9, 141(72.7%) participants belongs to nuclear family, 35(18%) participants parents were working as businessmen, 112(57.7%) participants falls in Scheduled tribe, 113(58.2%) participants belongs to Christian and 109(56.2%) participants belongs to rural area..

Table: 1.1.2

Title: To Compare Urban and Rural female Adolescents by assessing Life Skills

Variables		Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pre	Self-Awareness	Female	194	34.9278	5.93880	.42638
	Empathy	Female	194	34.0000	5.33441	.38299
	Effective Communication	Female	194	25.9381	4.19428	.30113
	IPR	Female	194	33.8196	4.96552	.35650
	Creative Thinking	Female	194	25.1546	4.99708	.35877
	Critical Thinking	Female	194	33.3660	5.54913	.39840
	Decision Making	Female	194	31.6907	4.87217	.34980
	Problem Solving	Female	194	30.2320	5.30644	.38098
	Coping With Emotion	Female	194	27.3866	5.58032	.40064
	Coping With Stress	Female	194	17.0825	5.31723	.38176
	Self-Awareness -	Female	194	37.3299	6.91356	.49636
	Empathy	Female	194	34.9021	5.24880	.37684
	Effective Communication	Female	194	25.5722	3.80175	.27295
	IPR	Female	194	34.1392	4.99598	.35869
	Creative Thinking	Female	194	26.0155	5.06893	.36393
	Critical Thinking	Female	194	36.1856	5.50521	.39525
	Decision Making	Female	194	33.3711	5.14317	.36926
	Problem Solving	Female	194	31.1031	6.60661	.47433
	Coping With Emotion	Female	194	29.9742	5.52004	.39632
	Coping With Stress	Female	194	19.2062	5.20947	.37402
Post						

The above table 1.1.2 represents the comparison of urban and rural female adolescents assessing Life Skills. From the above results, it is found that all the factors have undergone a change for most of the participants except for effective communication and critical thinking. This clearly shows the positive impact of the intervention given.

Table: 1.1.3

Title: Ho: There will be significant differences between female Adolescents on the basis of life skills intervention H₁: There will be no significant differences among female Adolescents on the basis of life skills intervention

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sig
Pre					
Self- Awareness	Female	194	34.9278	5.93880	.125
Empathy	Female	194	34.0000	5.33441	.691
Effective Communication	Female	194	25.9381	4.19428	.022
IPR	Female	194	33.8196	4.96552	.165
Creative Thinking	Female	194	25.1546	4.99708	.742
Critical Thinking	Female	194	33.3660	5.54913	.416
Decision Making	Female	194	31.6907	4.87217	.964
Problem Solving	Female	194	30.2320	5.30644	.856
Coping with Emotion	Female	194	27.3866	5.58032	.230
Coping with Stress	Female	194	17.0825	5.31723	.251
Self -Awareness	Female	194	37.3299	6.91356	.658
Empathy	Female	194	34.9021	5.24880	.552
Effective Communication	Female	194	25.5722	3.80175	.493
IPR	Female	194	34.1392	4.99598	.227
Creative Thinking	Female	194	26.0155	5.06893	.235
Critical Thinking	Female	194	36.1856	5.50521	.946
Decision Making	Female	194	33.3711	5.14317	.248
Problem Solving	Female	194	31.1031	6.60661	.609
Coping with Emotion	Female	194	29.9742	5.52004	.634
Coping with Stress	Female	194	19.2062	5.20947	.837

The above table 1.1.3 shows Comparison of female adolescents in terms of life skills intervention. The table shows significant difference in communication skills in pre-condition where the urban females were scoring better than rural female adolescents but after receiving the intervention rural female adolescents improved their communication and scored similar to urban female adolescents. This shows that the intervention has a considerable impact.

Discussion

The findings shows that out of 194 participants, 114(58.8%) participants belongs to the age group of 14-15 years, 85(43.8%) participants are studying in class 9, 141(72.7%) participants belongs to nuclear family, 35(18%) participants parents were working as businessmen, 112(57.7%) participants falls in Scheduled tribe, 113(58.2%) participants belongs to Christian and 109(56.2%) participants belongs to rural area. In the comparison of urban and rural female adolescents assessing Life Skills it is found that all the factors have undergone a change for most of the participants except for effective communication and critical thinking. This clearly shows the positive impact of the intervention given. The present finding are in support with Gopalakrishna (2014) and Khera & Khosla, (2012), studies where the findings shows that those adolescents undergone training possess positive co-relation between core affective life skill and self-concept and are better in all aspects. Therefore the intervention program was effective in enhancing the self-concept. The results of hypothesis shows that significant differences is found in communication skills in pre-condition where the urban females were scoring better than rural female adolescents but after receiving the intervention rural female adolescents improved their communication and scored similar to urban female adolescents. This shows that the intervention has a considerable impact on all scales of life skills

assessment. A sharp increase in scores is noticed in the scales of Self-Awareness, Empathy, Interpersonal Relationship, Creative Thinking, Decision Making, Problem Solving, Coping with Emotions, Coping with Stress, which means intervention has most effect in these areas. The present finding is in support with Anuradha (2014), study where the findings shows that adolescents scored reasonably a good score on life skills which showed that adolescents are well equipped with life skills.

Conclusion

The problems faced by the children of alcoholics are given less importance especially viewed in Indian Scenario. Parental alcoholism has severe effects on children of alcoholics; children develop low self-esteem and chronic depression. Even if the alcoholic gets treated and reformed himself but the family members who are greatly affected may not themselves ever recover from the problems inflicted upon them. Children of alcoholic are at risk and deserve more attention in prevention and early intervention of problems. The present study will bring forward awareness programmes for adolescents take necessary steps, actions and interventions which will enhance the quality of adolescents life, highlighting the need to support adolescents through professional development in engaging with the complexities involved, improved better home environment, building and strengthening good parent-child relationships and provide good support system from professionals and peer groups. Similarly several awareness programmes like distributing pamphlets, posters have been launched to awaken people and to keep them away from alcohol. The overall impact of de-addiction programme is positive, efforts should be made to make this programme continuous and the drive against alcoholism should be carried out on a war footing manner. Other professionals like mental health professionals or through teachers and parents should be involved in skill building exercises and promoting competence among adolescents.

References

- Anda, D. d., Baroni, S., Boskin, L., Buchwald, L., Morgan, J., Ow, J., et al. (2000). Stress, Stressors and Coping among High School Students. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 22(6), 441-463.
- Anuradha, K. (2014, February). Assessment of Life Skills Among Adolescents. *International Journal of Scientific Research*, 111(11).
- Gopalakrishna, R. (2014, April). Enhancement of Self Concept Using Life Skills Approach. *Research Direction Journal*, 1(10).
- Khera, S., & Khosla, S. (2012). A Study of Core Life Skills of Adolescents in Relation To Their Self Concept Developed Through YUVA School Life Skill Programme. *International Journal of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research*, 1(11), 115-125.
- Nair, A. R., Subasree, R., & Ranjan, S. (2010). *Manual for Life Skills Assessment Scale*. Chennai: Schools of Life Skills Education and Social Harmony Rajiv Gandhi National Institute of Youth Development.
- Pilat, J. M., & Jones, J. W. (1985). Identification of Children of Alcoholics: Two Empirical Studies. *Alcohol Health & Research World*, 9(2), 27-33.
- Raj, H., Kumar, K., Sinha, V. K., & Dogra, R. (2012). A Comparative Study on Behavioural Problems in Children of Alcohol Dependent Parents. *Dysphrenia*, 3, 137-143.
- Stanley, S., & Vanitha, C. (2008). Psychosocial Correlates in Adolescents Children of Alcoholics- Implications for Intervention. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 12(2), 67-80.

THE STUDY ON WOMEN AND SEXUAL IMPACT

Chetankumar T.M.
Raja Lakhamgouda Law College,
Belagavi – 590006, Karnataka

Delegation to the 2nd International Women's Rights Assembly
(Regd: 06IWRA2)

Abstract:

Of the different types of violence against women, sexual harassment is the commonest form of violence which women encounter in urban space in particular. Sexual harassment in the workplace is usually associated with a heterosexual employee making unwelcome sexual advances to another heterosexual employee of the opposite gender. And from a traditional perspective, sexual harassment is a demand that subordinates, usually women, and grant sexual favour to retain a job benefit.

Keywords: *Harassment, Impact, Justice, Remedy, Women.*

In every society women have a prominent position. The prominent role played by the women in her various stages of her life itself is sufficient evident to show her contribution in the family as well as in the society. In spite of her priceless contribution in the life of every individual; she still belongs to a vulnerable section of the society due to several social barriers and impediments. The position of Indian women is no better compared to their counterparts in other parts of the world. The rich and the poor alike are the victims of social barriers and disadvantages of varying kinds.¹

The difficulties for women seem to be never ending in the world. In the present context, women pass through the realms of practical life and the world can at last pleased about the presence of law against sexual harassment. The vulnerability of females to this repugnant offense has increased manifold. The patriarchal system, which is our principal social setup, not only limits men to engage in inhuman and immoral acts against women but also grants them the license to blatantly to prove false the prevalence of these prejudices that almost

every woman experiences at some point in her life.² In a conventional and male dominated society, women be inclined to remain silent on the prejudices they face because they fear that their image in the society will be ruined and that their own family will discourage them from working in organizations. The concept of sexual harassment is an old one, it was acknowledged as a socio-legal phenomenon in recent times. Sexual harassment has been recognized and addressed at international level by various organizations.³

Sexual harassment in the workplace refers to an verbal or physical act with a sexual nature. The verbal or physical acts with a sexual nature include:

- i. Joking or teasing with a sexual nature;

² Maheen Salman, Fahad Abdullah, Afia Saleem, *Sexual Harassment at Workplace and its Impact on Employee Turnover Intentions*, Business & Economic Review: Vol. 8, Issue 1: 2016, p. 87.

³ i. The International Confederation of Free Trade Unions,

ii. International Labour Organization,

iii. The United Nations Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women,

iv. The European Union.

¹ Dr. G.B. Reddy, *Women and the Law*, Gogia Law Agency, Hyderabad (2012) at p. vii.

- ii. Continuous invitation to dinner or date despite rejection;
- iii. Intentional dissemination of hearsay with a sexual nature;
- iv. Enquiring for or sharing sexual experience;
- v. Spreading and displaying a nude or image with apparent sexual contents;
- vi. Request for sexual intercourse;
- vii. Unnecessary physical contact;
- viii. Forced sexual intercourse, etc.⁴

The ILO Committee of Experts on the Application of Conventions and Recommendations, in the general observations on the application of the Discrimination Convention (1958, No. 111) in 2003, expressed the view that sexual harassment is a form of sex discrimination and should be addressed within the requirements of the Convention. Thus, in accordance with the Convention's requirements to prohibit sex discrimination and adopt a policy to promote equality of opportunity and treatment, measures should be taken to address sexual harassment.⁵

Sexual Harassment - Definition

To eliminate sexual harassment, efforts have been made both at the national and international level. There is no definition which explains about what exactly constitutes sexual harassment. At the international level the term sexual harassment has been broadly defined as a form of violence against women and as discriminatory treatment, while the same

term has been defined at the national level as, the laws relating to the sexual harassment focus more closely on the illegal conduct.⁶ At the international level, the United Nations General Recommendation 19⁷ defines sexual harassment as:

“Such unwelcome sexually determined behavior as physical contact and advances, sexually colored remarks, showing pornography and sexual demands, whether by words or actions. Such conduct can be humiliating and may constitute a health and safety problem; it is discriminatory when the woman has reasonable ground to believe that her objection would disadvantage her in connection with her employment, including recruitment or promotion, or when it creates a hostile working environment.”

The International Labor Organization (ILO) is a specialized United Nations agency that has addressed sexual harassment as a prohibited form of sex discrimination. The ILO has made clear that sexual harassment is more than a problem of safety and health, and unacceptable working conditions, but is also a form of violence primarily against women.⁸ The European Union (EU) and the Council of Europe (COE) address sexual harassment as illegal behavior. The European Commission of the EU defines sexual harassment as *“unwanted conduct of a sexual nature, or other conduct based on sex affecting the dignity of women and men at work. This includes unwelcome physical, verbal or nonverbal conduct”*.

The definitions of sexual harassment found at the international and regional level form the international law that prohibits sexual harassment. The first country which defines the terms sexual harassment was United States. It defines term as a prohibited form of

⁴ Guide on Prevention of Sexual Harassment in the Workplace, Compiled by Beijing Zhongze Women's Legal Consultation and Service Center – Women Watch China, International Labour Organization, December 2010.

http://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---asia/---ro-bangkok/---ilo-beijing/documents/publication/wcms_157626.pdf

⁵ ILO: General observation on Convention No. 111: Discrimination (Employment and Occupation), 1958, Report of the Committee of Experts on the Application of Conventions and Recommendations, Report III (Part 1A), International Labour Conference, 91st Session, Geneva, 2003, pp.463-464.

⁶ <http://hrlibrary.umn.edu/svaw/harassment/explore/1whatis.htm>

⁷ Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination Against Women

⁸ *Discrimination (Employment and Occupation) Convention (No. C111)*.

sex discrimination that violates the Title VII of the Civil Rights Act, 1964⁹. According to Employment Opportunity Commission (EEOC) the term sexual harassment has been defined as:

Unwelcome sexual advances, requests for sexual favors, and other verbal or physical conduct of a sexual nature, when

1. Submission to such conduct is made either explicitly or implicitly a term or condition of an individual's employment;
2. Submission to or rejection of such conduct by an individual is used as the basis for employment decisions affecting such individual; or
3. Such conduct has the purpose or effect of unreasonably interfering with an individual's work performance or creating an intimidating, hostile or offensive working environment.

According to Gutek and Done (2001) sexual harassment is defined as a legal and a psychological phenomenon. Legally, two types of sexual harassment were identified (a) quid pro quo (this for that) harassment that requires the employee to submit to sexual demands as a condition for promotion to avoid trouble, or being dismissed or in the case of faculty-student relationship, sex for better grades and (b) hostile-environment harassment where sexuality or discriminatory intimidation, ridicule, and insult are being practiced in the environment in which the employee works or students learn.¹⁰

Psychologists defined sexual harassment on the reasonableness of the offender. Sexual harassment is perceived as an act of unsuitable mind or lack of understanding as

prevents one from having the mental capacity required by law to enter into a particular relationship. Therefore, sexual harassment was seen as an act done as a result of mental imbalance.¹¹

The Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013¹² is an act "to provide protection against sexual harassment of women at workplace and for the prevention and redressal of complaints of sexual harassment."

The Act defines the term "sexual harassment" includes any one or more of the following unwelcome acts or behaviour (whether directly or by implication) namely:-

- (i) physical contact and advances; or
- (ii) a demand or request for sexual favours; or
- (iii) making sexually coloured remarks; or
- (iv) showing pornography; or
- (v) any other unwelcome physical, verbal or non-verbal conduct of sexual nature;¹³

The atrocious gang rape of a social worker in Rajasthan in 1997 brought to the attention of the Supreme Court of India, the absence of law led the Hon'ble judiciary to formulate effective measures to check the evil of sexual harassment of working women at all work places. The concern showed by the judiciary towards this made the Indian legislators to think seriously about this issue and finally the legislation has been enacted on prevention of sexual harassment against female employees at the workplace.

⁹ PUBLIC LAW 88-352-JULY 2, 1964

¹⁰ Carina Maris Amaka Okeke, *Impact of Sexual Harassment on Women Undergraduates' Educational Experience in Anambra State of Nigeria*, Seton Hall University Dissertations and Theses (ETDs), 2011, p. no. 31. See Gutek, B. A. & Done, R. (2001). Sexual harassment. In R. K. Unger (Ed.), *Handbook of the Psychology of Women and Gender*. New York: Wiley,

¹¹ *Ibid*, p. no. 32. See Browne, K. R. (1997). An evolutionary perspective on sexual harassment: Seeking roots in biology rather than ideology. *Journal of Contemporary Legal Issues*, 8.

¹² Act No. 14 OF 2013

¹³ Section 2(n) Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013.

The guidelines framed the Hon'ble judiciary in the *Vishaka Case*¹⁴ hopes to redress as well as prevent cases of sexual harassment. The key features of the guidelines framed in the Vishaka case is as under:

1. The law applies to women harassed in the workplace including women working as domestic workers, daily wagers, temporary or permanent, full-time or part-time, as well as volunteers. The women may or may not be employed and can be of any age. The law is only applicable to women and women only.
2. Sexual harassment includes any one or more of the following unwelcome acts or behavior:
 - Physical contact or advances
 - A demand or request for sexual favours
 - Making sexually coloured remarks
 - Showing pornography
 - Any other unwelcome physical, verbal or non-verbal conduct of sexual nature

If any act is done under the following circumstances that would also count as sexual harassment:

- Implied or explicit promise of preferential treatment in employment
 - Implied or explicit threat of detrimental treatment in employment
 - Implied or explicit threat about her present or future employment status
 - Interferes with work or creates an intimidating/hostile/offensive work environment
 - Humiliating treatment likely to affect her health and safety.¹⁵
3. The act of harassment can occur in the workplace and also if a woman is

¹⁴ (1997) 6 SCC 241, AIR 1997 SC 3011

¹⁵ The guideline of the judiciary has been inserted under Section 3(2) of Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013.

harassed while visiting a place arising out of or during the course of employment including transportation provided by the office, a complaint can be filed under this Act.

4. The Act requires all workplaces to set up Internal Complaints Committees to address the issue of sexual harassment. There will also be a Local Complaints Committee for each District where complaints can be filed.
5. An aggrieved woman can file a complaint within 3 months of the incident (or later if allowed by the committee).
6. The Act provides the option of a settlement between the aggrieved woman and the responded through conciliation but only on the request of the woman. However, money compensation cannot be a basis for the settlement.
7. The inquiry has to be completed within 90 days.
8. In case of malicious complaints or false evidence, the Committee may take action against the woman/person. However, simply not being able to prove an allegation will not mean that it is a false/malicious complaint.
9. The identity of the aggrieved woman, respondent, witnesses as well as other details of the complaint cannot be published or disclosed to the public/media.
10. The Act also hopes to prevent such incidents by placing a duty on employers to hold regular workshops/awareness programmes as well as, display the consequences of harassment in the workplace. Every employer has a duty to provide a safe working environment to all employees.¹⁶

Impact of Sexual Harassment

Violence against women can have a myriad of devastating consequences on women's short and long-term health and wellbeing.

¹⁶ <http://www.indiatvnews.com/news/india/10-things-to-know-about-law-relating-to-sexual-harassment-at-wor-30985.html>

Along with the immediate physical and emotional impacts of violence, women's overall quality of life can be adversely affected over an entire lifetime, which can, in turn, impact their participation and engagement in various aspects of life and society.¹⁷

Sexual harassment may be manifested in both verbal and physical conduct. The use of objects of pictures to harass the victim is also another form of harassment.¹⁸ Some examples of verbal, non-verbal and physical harassment as follows

VERBAL

- Whistling at someone
- Making sexual comments about a person's body
- Making sexual comments or innuendos
- Turning work discussions to sexual topics
- Telling sexual jokes or stories
- Asking about sexual fantasies, preferences, or history
- Making kissing sounds, howling, and smacking lips
- Making sexual comments about a person's clothing, anatomy, or looks
- Repeatedly asking out a person who is not interested
- Telling lies or spreading rumors about a person's personal sex life

NON-VERBAL

- Looking a person up and down (Elevator eyes)
- Staring at someone
- Blocking a person's path
- Following the person
- Giving personal gifts
- Displaying sexually suggestive visuals
- Making sexual gestures with hands or through body movements
- Making facial expressions such as winking, throwing kisses, or licking lips

¹⁷ <http://www.statcan.gc.ca/pub/85-002-x/2013001/article/11766/11766-3-eng.htm>

¹⁸ <http://www.pcw.gov.ph/sites/default/files/documents/resources/sexual%20harassment1.pdf>

PHYSICAL

- Giving a massage around the neck or shoulders
- Touching the person's clothing, hair, or body
- Hugging, kissing, patting, or stroking
- Touching or rubbing oneself sexually around another person
- Standing close or brushing up against another person¹⁹

Harassment is associated with increased risk of anxiety, depression, and posttraumatic stress disorder as well as diminished self-esteem, self confidence, and psychological well-being.²⁰ According to stress theory, group differences in mental health and well-being result from disparities in exposure to stressors and access to personal and social resources that allow individuals to cope with stressful experiences. Stressful experiences are expected to be particularly deleterious to mental health when they are chronic, negative, and unpredictable; are a threat to one's identity; or signify a failure to achieve a desired goal. Louise Fitzgerald, Sandra L. Shullman and Schneider, Kimberly T. has developed an integrated theoretical model that identifies the causes and consequences of workplace sexual harassment. They identify possible experiences of sexual harassment, including individual and workplace characteristics. They also hypothesize that sexual harassment is a stressor that can lead to work withdrawal, career instability, job dissatisfaction, and poor mental and physical health.

When a person is forced, pressurized and manipulated for unwanted sexual activity, when she or he is unable to consent due to age, illness, disability, or the influence of

¹⁹ <http://www.un.org/womenwatch/osagi/pdf/whatissh.pdf>

²⁰ Jason N. Houle, Jeremy Staff, Jeylan T. Mortimer, Christopher Uggen, and Amy Blackstone, *The Impact of Sexual Harassment on Depressive Symptoms during the Early Occupational Career*, Society and Mental Health 1(2), American Sociological Association 2011, P. No. 89.

alcohol or other drugs there is more possibility of sexual violence. Sexual violence can be done in various ways like rape, incest, child sexual assault, ritual abuse, nonstranger rape, statutory rape, marital or partner rape, sexual exploitation, sexual contact, sexual harassment, exposure, and voyeurism. It is considered as crime not only because of sexual desire but by the desire to control, humiliate and harm. It violates the trust and feelings of safety of the person subjected to sexual violence. It can, and does, happen to people of all ages, races, genders, sexual orientations, religions, professions, incomes, and ethnicities. Sexual violence affects all of us: survivors, significant others, communities, and society.²¹

Sexual violence results in negative impact on daily life not to the person who is victim but also on their survivors also. Each survivor reacts to sexual violence in their own unique way. There are long-term and short-term impacts of sexual violence on overall health and well-being. Common emotional reactions include guilt, shame, fear, lack of sensation, shock, and feelings of segregation. The psychological effects of sexual violence have been linked to long-term health risk behaviors. Physical impacts may include personal injuries, concerns about pregnancy, or risk of contracting. Economic impacts of sexual violence include medical expenses and time off work.

Sexual violence can affect parents, friends, partners, children, spouses, and/or coworkers of the survivor. As they try to make sense of what happened, loved ones may experience similar reactions and feelings to those of the survivor. Fear, guilt, self-blame, and anger are a few common reactions.²² Sexual violence also affects the feelings of communities at large. The communities like

cultural and religious, neighbors, workplace, campuses may feel fear, anger or disbelief. If sexual assault happened than the above communities they feel very bad. Sexual violence tears at the fabric of community well-being. Additionally, there are financial costs to communities. These costs include medical services, criminal justice expenses, crisis and mental health services fees, and the lost contributions of individuals affected by sexual violence.

The contributions and achievements that may never come as a result of sexual violence represent a cost to society that cannot be measured. Sexual violence endangers critical societal structures because it creates a climate of violence and fear. Sexual harassment alone cost the federal government an estimated \$327 million in losses associated with job turnover, sick leave, and individual and group productivity among federal employees.²³

The effect of sexual assault on women takes many forms – some lasting short while and others lasting for long. Men can experience sexual assault, but assault on women is far more prevalent. The mental and physical effects of sexual assault on women include:

- *Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD)* – Victims may experience severe anxiety, stress, and fear as an effect of sexual assault.
- *Substance Abuse* – Women sexual assault victims may use alcohol or drugs to dull their emotional suffering and pain.
- *Self-Harm* – Some sexual assault victims may harm themselves by cutting or other means.
- *Depression* – Depression represents one of the most common effects of sexual assault on women.
- *Sexually Transmitted Disease (STD)* – Perpetrators of sexual violence may infect their victims with STDs.

²¹https://studentaffairs.duke.edu/sites/default/files/u7/NSVRC_Publication_Factsheet_Impact-of-sexual-violence.pdf

²²http://www.nsvrc.org/sites/default/files/saam_2016_impact-of-sexual-violence.pdf

²³ According to 1995 U.S. Merit Systems Protection Board

- *Pregnancy* – Sometimes, assault on women may result in pregnancy.
- *Flashbacks* – Some victims become tormented by flashback memories that make it seem as if the sexual assault is happening all over again.
- *Eating Disorders* – Frequently, victims of sexual assault may use food to control and cope with their negative emotions. Using food in this way can result in the development of eating disorders, such as anorexia nervosa and bulimia.
- *Sleep Disorders* – Sexual assault survivors may develop sleep disorders characterized by sleeping too much or not being able to sleep.
- *Body Memories* – Frequently referred to as psychosomatic symptoms, body memories occur in the form of physical problems like headaches, migraines, digestive issues, light headedness, or dizziness that medical examinations cannot explain.²⁴

Violence against women world-wide indicate that violence is an issue that permeates every corner of society, is widespread and costly. A common way to organize the economic costs of violence is to place them in categories based on the consequences of violence and the services utilized as a result of violence. Costs can be found in seven major categories:

- Justice,
- Health,
- Social Services,
- Education,
- Business Costs,
- Personal or Household Costs and
- Intangibles

²⁴ <http://www.healthypplace.com/abuse/sexual-assault/effect-of-sexual-assault-on-women-sexual-assault-victims/>

Justice

Justice costs include policing, court trials, penal costs and related costs such as victim compensation, administering community sentences, and organizations that support the incarcerated. They can include labour, capital and material inputs.

Health

Health is another area that is expensive for the state, and also for individuals depending on the extent to which health care is publicly or privately funded. Health costs result from both direct and indirect health concerns caused by violence. They can also be both short and long-term.

Social Services

Social costs stem from the provision of public services to both victims and perpetrators of violence against women. They can be privately or publicly funded. Social services include social welfare agencies helping abused women, abusive men and their children.

Education

Education costs can include the added demand for special education services related to behavioural problems and learning disabilities in children who witness abuse at home, as well as school programs with the aim of reducing violence against girls.

Business and Employment Costs

When violence happens at home, the woman's paid work environment is affected as well. These effects have a serious impact on the business sector. Business costs include her lost time at work and reduced attention, the time her co-workers spend covering for her, the time she may spend in the restroom or on the phone with friends or family, actual time she may need to take off work, administrative time spent processing

her time off, administrative costs for the search and training of a replacement employee if she leaves the job, administration costs for programs or policies designed to help support her, lost profits from her decrease in output, and the increase in overtime payments to other workers who cover for her.

Household and Personal

Many personal and household costs result from violence against women. Victims spend a great deal in direct out-of-pocket costs for such things as transportation, childcare, alternative therapies, replacing destroyed belongings, relocation, and medications. These expenditures greatly affect household consumption, skewing it away from the goods and services that would be chosen in the absence of violence.

Intangibles

Many consequences of violence are not tangible. Intangibles are very difficult to cost, and many studies do not attempt to do so. Nevertheless they represent very important and significant costs. A few examples include the fear that women harbour as a result of abuse; pain and suffering or the loss of life; and second generation effects of violence. It is impossible to measure the costs associated with fear and, while attempts have been made at developing measures of pain and suffering or loss of life, they are imprecise at best. Finally, second generation effects are well-documented but also not easy to measure.²⁵

Conclusion

The concept of sexual harassment can be experienced in both developing and

developed nations. Sexual harassment is existed in India for a long time. Under Article 19(1)(g) of the Constitution of India it has been recognized as an infringement of the fundamental rights of Women. The efforts of the Women's movement and human rights concern, an increasing number of women are come forward to reporting such cases and fight for their legal rights in the judiciary. The provisions of the Indian Constitution like Article 14, 15, and 21 protects against all forms of discrimination. To eliminate all forms of discrimination against women including sexual harassment there is need of reform in our criminal justice system. Sexual harassment affects the values of women from all corners may be social values, cultural values and economical values. The impact of sexual harassment will not affect only the women but also her surroundings, family, parents, neighbor and society at large. There is a need to put an end for all sorts of violence against women at workplace, education and all other forms. There is need both at the national and international level to have a effective law and effective implementation of the same.

References

1. Maheen Salman, Fahad Abdullah, Afia Saleem, *Sexual Harassment at Workplace and its Impact on Employee Turnover Intentions*, Business & Economic Review: Vol. 8, Issue 1: 2016.
2. *Guide on Prevention of Sexual Harassment in the Workplace*, Compiled by Beijing Zhongze Women's Legal Consultation and Service Center – Women Watch China, International Labour Organization, December 2010.
3. Dr. G.B. Reddy, *Women and the Law*, Gogia Law Agency, Hyderabad (2012).
4. <http://hrlibrary.umn.edu/svaw/harassment/explore/1whatis.htm>
5. <http://www.indiatvnews.com/news/india/10-things-to-know-about-law->

²⁵ Tanis Day, Katherine McKenna, Audra Bowlus, *The Economic Costs of Violence Against Women: An Evaluation of the Literature*, United Nations Unies, 2005, P. No. 7-10.

- relating-to-sexual-harassment-at-wor-30985.html.
6. <http://www.pcw.gov.ph/sites/default/files/documents/resources/sexual%20harassment1.pdf>
 7. <http://www.un.org/womenwatch/osa/gi/pdf/whatish.pdf>
 8. Carina Maris Amaka Okeke, *Impact of Sexual Harassment on Women Undergraduates' Educational Experience in Anambra State of Nigeria*, Seton Hall University Dissertations and Theses (ETDs), 2011.
 9. Jason N. Houle, Jeremy Staff, Jeylan T. Mortimer, Christopher Uggen, and Amy Blackstone, *The Impact of Sexual Harassment on Depressive Symptoms during the Early Occupational Career*, Society and Mental Health 1(2), American Sociological Association 2011.
 10. http://www.nsvrc.org/sites/default/files/saam_2016_impact-of-sexual-violence.pdf
 11. https://studentaffairs.duke.edu/sites/default/files/u7/NSVRC_Publication_Factsheet_Impact-of-sexual-violence.pdf
 12. <http://www.healthyplace.com/abuse/sexual-assault/effect-of-sexual-assault-on-women-sexual-assault-victims/>
 13. <http://www.statcan.gc.ca/pub/85-002-x/2013001/article/11766/11766-3-eng.htm>
 14. Tanis Day, Katherine McKenna, Audra Bowlus, *The Economic Costs of Violence Against Women: An Evaluation of the Literature*, United Nations Unies, 2005.
 15. Nipan Haloi, *Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace: Its Preventive Measures*, International Research Journal of Interdisciplinary & Multidisciplinary Studies (IRJIMS), Volume-I, Issue-VII, August 2015.

RIGHT TO ABORTION IS A BASIC HUMAN RIGHT: SPECIAL REFERENCE TO INDIA

Pyali Chatterjee

Phd Scholar under the Supervision of Dr. Komal Vig
Amity University, Noida, UP

Delegation to the 2nd International Women's Rights Assembly
(Regd: 05IWRA2)

Abstract:

This In a country like India, where everyday people fight for reservation rights and Right to equality under Article 14 and 21 of Indian Constitution, but there is one right which needs fight or movement to bring this right for every women of India i.e. Abortion Rights under Article 21. Indian women were silent regarding their abortion rights protected under Article 21. Here in India only married woman were given abortion rights under Medical Termination of Pregnancy of Pregnancy Act, 1971 but that too also under certain conditions which is mentioned under Section 3 of the MTP Act. Explanation 2 of Section 3 of MTP Act says that "Where any pregnancy occurs as a result of failure of any device or method used by any married woman or her husband for the purpose of limiting the number of children, the anguish caused by such unwanted pregnancy may be presumed to constitute a grave injury to the mental health of the pregnant woman". Now question is why only married women were given this right and not to the other ladies. Recently when live together was declared legal in India after the decision of Payal Katara – Vs – Superintendent Nari Niketan Kandri Vihar Agra and others, but no amendment is done in MTP Act for including women who get conceived from this relation. In US abortion rights is considered to be as one of the basic rights of the women after the feminist movement for abortion rights lead by Margaret Sanger and many more. And due to this now women in US were enjoying their rights without any distinction. Even many, International Organization recognized this right to be as one of the basic human rights. In India, abortions was introduced as a family planning method and not as a right because of which only married women were allowed to go for abortion and that too only when she conceived due to failure of any contraceptives. So here women don't have any choice. In India, there is a strong need of feminist movement like in US, so that Indian women can enjoy this right i.e. Right to Abortion. Through this paper researcher will discuss about the violation of right of unmarried women, widow, and divorcee in terms of abortion right.

Keywords: *Abortion, Right to equality, Feminist, Pro-Choice, Reproductive Choice*

Very human is equal in the eye of god as well as in the eye of law. But when questions comes about the rights and position of women in society then one can find the clear discrimination between men and women. Even if we remember the Delhi gang rape case or Nirbhaya case where

defense lawyers put the entire blame on the victim and make a rubbish and ridiculous statement that "If you keep sweets on the street then dogs will come and eat them. Why did Nirbhaya's parents send her with anyone that late at night? He was not her boyfriend. Is it not the parents' responsibility

to keep an eye on where she goes and with whom?"¹ This example is to explain that how women were treated in our society and the discrimination made by the society. This kind of discrimination shows the low mentality of the person but this is not the actual problem of the women. Because there are only few peoples who holds or keep such kind of thinking. At least here women can fight against such people for the protection of their dignity. But, what if Government makes any law which is discriminating and bias in nature, a law which discriminate between married woman with unmarried, widow, divorcee etc like Section 3 of The Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971 i.e. abortion right.

Theoretically in many court cases and even the most important document i.e. Universal Declaration of Human Rights also states that "All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood."² Even Constitution of India also says the same thing under Article 14 that "The State shall not deny to any person equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws within the territory of India."³ But practically when it has to be apply in situation, when question arise regarding it applicability then the problem is that this right is limited to book only. Especially, when it comes about the abortion right of the women, that whether all women has abortion right irrespective of their marital status? As we know that under MTP Act, 1971 only married, rape victim and minor girls were allowed to go for legal abortion. And for the rest there is no such right i.e. for unmarried, widow and for divorcee law is

silent in India. And the question which comes in our mind is about the applicability of the Article 14 in this situation that why all women were not treated equally before Law? Why there is biasness regarding the applicability of MTP laws in India. As MTP laws are solely for the benefit of the women then also women were not allowed to enjoy their basic right.

PRE- ABORTION LAW: INDIAN PENAL CODE

Before MTP Act any kind of abortion was illegal and punishable under Indian Penal Code, 1860. Section 312 -316 deals with it. Abortion which was done in good faith for saving the life of the mother was only the ground for legal abortion. Also abortion was allowed in the cases of rape victim. But due to the strict abortion laws many women has to choose illegal ways because of which women has to undergo punishment if caught in the hand of law or sometime they lost their life due to the unhygienic methods which she used for abortion. Because of this only during second wave of feminism in US, women all together start the abortion right movement in USA. Margret Sanger was one of the known face of the Second wave feminism as she was the person who initiate this fight for all women irrespective of their caste, color, race etc and later after Roe versus wade 410 US 113 (1973), abortion was made legal for all women. Not only that many international organization considered abortion as one of the essential human right for women which I will discuss later on. In India abortion law was introduced in 1971 but not as a right for women but as family planning method. It was introduced by a committee i.e. Shantilal Shah Committee and on the basis of the report of this committee, abortion law was introduced in India.

POST ABORTION LAWS: MEDICAL TERMINATION OF PREGNANCY ACT

As the law relating to abortion was very strict in India to make the law liberal and to

¹ Abhinav Garg, The Times of India, Mar 4, 2015, 09.25 AM,

<http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/Defence-lawyers-blame-Nirbhaya-for-rape/articleshow/46451407.cms>

² Article 1,

http://www.ohchr.org/EN/UDHR/Documents/UDHR_Translations/eng.pdf

³ <https://indiankanon.org/doc/367586/>

protect the women life from illegal abortion MTP Act was enacted. But this law was enacted not to provide this law as a right to women but it was introduced as a family planning method to control the population which any one can interpret from the language of the Section-3 of the Act.

“3. When Pregnancies may be terminated by registered medical practitioners.-

(1) Notwithstanding anything contained in the Indian Penal Code (45 of 1860), a registered medical practitioner shall not be guilty of any offence under that Code or under any other law for the time being in

force, if any pregnancy is terminated by him in accordance with the provisions of this Act.

(2) Subject to the provisions of sub-section (4), a pregnancy may be terminated by a registered medical practitioner,-

(a) Where the length of the pregnancy does not exceed twelve weeks if such medical practitioner is, or

(b) Where the length of the pregnancy exceeds twelve weeks but does not exceed twenty weeks, if not less than two registered medical practitioners are.

Of opinion, formed in good faith, that,- (i) the continuance of the pregnancy would involve a risk to the life of the pregnant woman or of grave injury physical or mental health ; or

(ii) There is a substantial risk that if the child were born, it would suffer from such physical or mental abnormalities as to be seriously handicapped.

Explanation 1.-Where any, pregnancy is alleged by the pregnant woman to have been caused by rape, the anguish caused by such pregnancy shall be presumed to constitute a

grave injury to the mental health of the pregnant woman.

Explanation 2.-Where any pregnancy occurs as a result of failure of any device or method used by any married woman or her husband for the purpose of limiting the number of children, the anguish caused by such unwanted pregnancy may be presumed to constitute a grave injury to the mental health of the pregnant woman.

(3) In determining whether the continuance of pregnancy would involve such risk of injury to the health as is mentioned in sub-section (2), account may be taken of the pregnant woman's actual or reasonable foreseeable environment.

(4) (a) No pregnancy of a woman, who has not attained the age of eighteen years, or, who, having attained the age of eighteen years, is a lunatic, shall be terminated except with the consent in writing of her guardian.

(b) Save as otherwise provided in Cl. (a), no pregnancy shall be terminated except with the consent of the pregnant woman.”⁴

Section 3 of the MTP act explains about the conditions when abortion can be performed by the doctors. The section clearly says that doctor opinion is must for performing abortion in women. Women wishes for abortion has given no importance in MTP Act as well as in pre abortion laws. Also Explanation 2 of the same says that only married women were allowed for abortion and that too also only when she can proof that the pregnancy was caused due to the failure of any contraceptive. And now question comes that why in 21st century still women has to proof that pregnancy was caused due to failure of any contraceptive methods. When two finger tests in rape victim is considered to be violative under Article 21 i.e. Right to privacy, then why

⁴ The Medical Termination Of Pregnancy Act, 1971, <http://tcw.nic.in/Acts/MTP-Act-1971.pdf>

Explanation 2 of section 3 of MTP Act is not considered to be as violative to Article 21. Why in India Abortion laws is biased in terms of its applicability. If a women wants abortion it means that the pregnancy is unwanted then for an unwanted pregnancy why she has to give answer to the question of the doctors. Don't we think that this question can really hurt one feelings, privacy etc. Also one more important point to discuss here is that this laws was introduced to protect the mother life from the hand of dai's or untrained professional who performed abortion. But when the law is restricted up to married women, rape victim and minor then in such case where the other lady will go for abortion, for them there is only one way that is illegal abortion.

Even during one of my research related to Abortion topic⁵, I have taken interview of Dr. Nehha V Motghare, MBBS, DGO, (CGMC 96/2003), during the conversation she said that many Doctors in private hospitals performed abortion in unmarried woman/girl while charging huge amounts. And no data or record is maintained for that. Now in one hand MTP Laws was enacted to protect the mother life and to control the illegal abortion but in the next hand because of it bias applicability it promotes the illegal business of the doctors by forcing the unmarried lady, widow, divorcee and also some time the women who are in a relation of adultery. Then what is the importance of this law. As before this law, abortion was allowed to protect the mother life, rape victim and now also it is allowed. The only new thing which was added is that that married women and minor were allowed for abortion. So, new law is not that effective to control the maternal death due to illegal abortion. Not only that even in many cases police also don't registered any cases if the abortion is done for the better future of the widow/divorcee. As in such cases pregnancy

might cause hurdle in the future of the women. Here in India, Government speak about women empowerment but how it is possible if the women were not able to enjoy their basic right. Also abortion right should not be limited to married women to get rid from unwanted pregnancy. But it should be allowed to every woman. As each single child will be part of the India Population. And also for the bright future of India, it's better to bring wanted child and not unwanted child. Because many unwanted child lost their life in the jaw of the street dog or in the garbage and if they are lucky then they might get shelter in any orphanage home. In every way Section 3 of the MTP Act is violative to Article 14 and 21. Not only it is violative to women rights for abortion but also against each and every unwanted child.

There are many international organizations which strictly criticize the use of abortion as family planning methods like World Population Conference of 1984 "The World Population Plan of Action recognizes, as one of its principles, the basic human right of all couples and individuals have the basic right to decide freely and responsibly the number and spacing of their children. For this right to be realized, couples and individuals must have access to the necessary education, information and means to regulate their fertility, regardless of the overall demographic goals of the Government"⁶

Then, the Principle 8 of the International Conference on Population and Development ICPD states that "Everyone has the right to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health. States should take all appropriate measures to ensure, on a basis of equality of men and women, universal access to health-care services, including those related to

⁵ Pyali Chatterjee, Medical Termination Of Pregnancy Act: A Boon Or A Bane For A Woman In India- A Critical Analysis, IJSR, ISSN: 2319-7064(Online), <https://www.ijsr.net/archive/v5i9/ART20161470.pdf>

⁶ Siddhivinayak Hirve, Abortion Policy in India: Lacunae and Future Challenges, CEHAT Mumbai, 2004, <http://www.cehat.org/go/uploads/AapIndia/hirve.pdf>

reproductive health care, which includes family planning and sexual health. Reproductive health-care programmer should provide the widest range of services without any form of coercion. All couples and individuals have the basic right to decide freely and responsibly the number and spacing of their children and to have the information, education and means to do so.

Article 2 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that “Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status. Furthermore, no distinction shall be made on the basis of the political, jurisdictional or international status of the country or territory to which a person belongs, whether it be independent, trust, non-self-governing or under any other limitation of sovereignty.”⁷

In the above three laws one thing which is common that law should be equal for all and abortion should not be used as family planning methods. But under MTP act, abortion is used as family planning methods. And Article 14 of Indian constitution fails to protect the abortion right of every woman. Also, when we speak about the choice of the women in India regarding the abortion rights it is to be mentioned here that, actually there is no choice given to the women. The law was enacted to protect the women life from the illegal abortion but for abortion the sole decision is depend on the medical practioner to decide to whether to perform abortion or not. Women willingness has given no importance here.

Even one of the Supreme Court judge AK Sikri, while speaking at the symposium “Reproductive Rights In Indian Courts:

⁷ Universal Declaration of Human Rights, http://www.ohchr.org/EN/UDHR/Documents/UDHR_Translations/eng.pdf

Celebrating Progress, Identifying Challenges And Discussing The Way Forward”organised by the Jindal Global University (JGU) said that “When we talk of reproductive rights in this country, then there is hardly any choice so far as the woman is concerned ...I can't help but wonder how we as humans have failed humanity. I am perplexed as to how in the 21st century, with all the technological advances, becoming frequent guests in the outer space and creating artificial intelligence, we are still not able to bring our women to enjoy the fruits of humanity. That is the harsh reality,”⁸ Actually there is no right given to the women in terms of Reproductive Rights or Abortion Rights. In both this situation woman has to depend on others decision. In present scenario woman individual decision has given no importance. As for MTP husband consent is not required. But under family law if a woman did abortion without taking husband permission or consent then it become a ground for divorce. It was in the case of Satya (Smt.) – Vs – Shri Ram AIR 1983 P & H 252: 1983 Hindu LR 117 : 1983 Marri LJ 153 :1983 Pun LJ 192,⁹ where court held that abortion done by wife without taking husband consent will amount to cruelty. This case also speaks about the harsh reality of woman position in Indian Society. The position of woman is just like the situation which we faced last year during demonetization of old currency, where we had money in our account but unavailable to use it due to shortage of new currency. But still there was a hope that this problem will be solved shortly after the available of the new currency. But in the life of the woman there is no such hope that when they will be able to enjoy the Reproductive Right and abortion Right. As, here the choice is on the

⁸ Mohak Gupta, Her body, her right: Women have the right to decide on pregnancy, SC judge says, [Indiatoday.in, February 11, 2017, http://indiatoday.intoday.in/story/women-right-decide-pregnancy-sc-judge-ak-sikri/1/880596.html](http://indiatoday.intoday.in/story/women-right-decide-pregnancy-sc-judge-ak-sikri/1/880596.html)

⁹Justice Palock Basu, Law Relating to protection of human rights,249(Modern law Publication, 2nd edn, 2007)

Government whether to give this right or not?

Honestly saying women in India should also start movement for their abortion right like in USA. May be after this only women will get the basic right i.e. Right to abortion.

SUGGESTION AND CONCLUSION

Equality before law and equal protection before law is the right of every one. Any biasness in law is the violation of the Article 14 of the Indian Constitution. If we consider Kelson Grundnorm theory, then Constitution of India is the grundnorm because from its other law derive it norms. Any law ultra-vires to Constitution is not a good law.

in the Part III of the constitution i.e. Fundamental Rights. So any law violative to any article of fundamental rights will not be considered as good law. Then, how Section-3 of the MTP Act is still operative as it's clearly violates the rights of every woman to enjoy the Abortion Right. It's the women who conceive, its she who carry the baby for 9 months, if she is not ready to give birth to a child then nobody has this right to forced her to give birth to a unwanted child or forced to choose the illegal way for abortion which is not at all good for our country reputation as well as for the woman health also. In 21st century when we talked about modernization and giving equal status to men and women then why such law still exists which itself discriminate a women from another woman. There are many job where married women were not allowed to join then in such situation if any of this woman conceived during live-in-relationship or from love affair then what will be her future, her career will be in stake or finished. A country like India, which is unable to protect or provide one of the important basic right to a woman, then how it will become a developed country like USA. A country will developed only when its citizen will grow and developed. And for this law should be equal for all.

It's high time for Indian women to start a feminist movement for abortion rights for all without any discrimination. Section -3 of the MTP Act should be amended as it's clearly violets Article 14 and 21 of the Constitution of India.

REFERENCE

- K.D. Gaur, Text Book on The Indian Penal Code, 559-560(Universal Publication Co. PVT. Ltd., 4th edn. 2009)
- Malini Karkal , Reproductive Rights and Reproductive Health of Women, http://www.womenstudies.in/elib/rep_health/rh_reproductive_rights.pdf
- Datar Versus Union of India, HRLN, Center for Reproductive Rights, New York, https://www.reproductiverights.org/sites/crr.civicactions.net/files/documents/Datar_v_India.pdf
- David J. Garrow, Liberty and Sexuality,(University of California Press, 1st paperback edn, 1998)
- S.G. Kabra, Abortion in India, Rawat Publication, Jaipur, 2013
- Osho, A new vision of womens's liberation, 71, Full Circle, New Delhi, First reprint, 2004
- Margaret Walters, Feminism A Very Short Introduction, Oxford University Press Inc, New york, 1st edn. 2005.

RIGHT PORTRAYAL OF WOMEN IN INDIAN ADVERTISEMENTS IN ELECTRONIC MEDIA

Suheba Khan

Phd Scholar (Center for Women's Studies)
Aligarh Muslim University

Delegation to the 2nd International Women's Rights Assembly
(Regd: 10IWRA2)

Abstract:

This paper is based on secondary data collected through different books and published journals. Television advertisements also collected for analysis. An explanatory and exploratory method is used to write this paper. The paper focus on the representation of women in Indian advertisements specifically those run on television from last 10 years. How these advertisements portray women on television through a very short and effective tool of media that leave a great impression on people's minds. The paper will focus on the objectification of women's body in different advertisements as sex objects. It will also focus on how these advertisements reinforce stereotypical image of women through patriarchal norms and values like the rightful place of women is always in home or look beautiful is the most important duty of a young women or for working women it is also important to manage the home front.

Keywords: *Advertisement, Gender, Objectification, Patriarchy, Stereotyping.*

Mass media are cultural forces that do not simply reflect but indirectly helps in shaping social realities. Life styles are often adopted through a complex process of imitation and comparison with attitudes and behavior presented by mass media. From feminist perspective mass media plays an important role in communicating women's issues, agendas, actions, etc. It can play a crucial role in popularizing women's perception, goals, rights, movements for equality etc and it can also have the power to make such things visible in the eyes of common people. But it helps in enforcing the patriarchal agenda as well. Media affects the mind sets of people; change the perception about themselves and the society among them, change in priority about their needs, etc.

“According to the study conducted jointly by federation of Indian chamber of commerce and industry (FICCI) and price water house

corporation private limited (PWC), television held the largest share (59%) in the entertainment industry followed by films (28%), music (12%) and radio (1%)”.

-Rommel Rodrigues (2005)

Advertisements are effective tool of mass media which impart knowledge and information with a dash of entertainment. Advertising affect our daily life consciously and unconsciously and are responsible to play a significant role in shaping the society in a much broader perspective. Advertising is a vital marketing tool that enables the firms to communicate directly with the consumer. Therefore, ads are made with the intention to seek viewer attention and response. Advertising apart from selling products or brands also sell attitude, behavior or life style. On an average an adult spends about two years of his life watching TV advertisements. It is presumed that viewing

these advertisements affect the viewer's attitudes and preferences. Advertisers have long been enamored with women and culture. Most of the advertisements portray women as the torch-bearers of cultural heritage. They are often portrayed in stereotypical images. She could be a wife, mother, daughter-in-law or mother-in-law. A common sight of women in advertisement for decades is in the kitchen, cooking food, washing bucket-full clothes, or feeding husband or children. Advertisers have also been accused for objectifying women's bodies. Nudity and sexuality of women are often used to gain consumer's attention. Most of the time women's appearance may not even be appropriate to the product being advertised. Women are often dressed in indecent attires with a sensuous gaze. The depiction of Women in Indian media be it films, television serials, news, media, visual advertisement is indeed an area of great concern.

Objective of the Study

As part of the audio visual media, advertisements are very important when it comes to influencing the choices and attitudes of people. But these advertisements have been accused of portraying women in negatively manner and ignoring the real aspects of women's lives by feminists. Women are either portrayed in typical traditional ways: busy in doing household chores, or if they are outside the home they are portrayed as mere a sex object with possible shortest clothes. The main objectives of this paper are:

- To study the portrayal of women in advertisements of different brands or products. How these advertisements portray women on television through a very short and effective tool of media that leave a great impression on people's minds.
- To study the objectification of women's body as an object in advertisements that women are often used as a piece of

decoration to attract the audience, when sometimes they are not even needed for the product being advertised.

- To study the negative impact of this portrayal of women's body that sometimes leads to the violence against women.

Review of Literature

Valdivia, Angharad N. (2004) in her edited book A Companion to Media Studies discussed that advertisers recognized that it has been so long portraying women in stereotypical roles, so they started to change the depiction to some extent. They try to address women's concern but on the other hand they bluff with the audience thorough their campaigns that equality has achieved. But close examination of such advertisements reveal that they reinforce same stereotypes in modern manner. The change in the image of women is not enough, the change must be occur in the mind set of advertisers and in the social system that surrounds us. Women are needed to be portrayed in strong independent public figures like politicians or athletes.

Linda Lazier and Alice Kendrick (1993) in their article women in advertisements: sizing up the images roles and functions, found out that the portrayal of women in the advertisements of television and print media has not change over the period of time. They claim that women in advertisements are not seen as important decision makers although they make important financial decision at home. Further the contribution of women in the workforce has been ignored by the advertisers socially and statistically and stereotypes that are used in the advertisements ignore the complex lives of modern women.

Perse, Elizabeth M. (2001). In her book Media Effects and Society talks about the effects of media on the society; one of the worst effects of media on society is through sexual content which is opposed by many

feminists. They claim that it is harmful for women as it promote objectification of women's body, sexualisation of women, discrimination against women and support a society that accept violence against women very easily. According to feminists pornography is the main sexual media content that de-values and de-humanizes women in eyes of men.

Prasad, Kiran (2006) in her edited book Women, Globalization and Mass Media discussed that though there are some changes in the campaigning of advertisements portraying women, but still these women are not out of the traditional limitations. If a woman is portrayed working outside the home, she is also a good house wife who manages both office and home. Again and again the primary duty of women as a good house wife is re enforced by the advertisers. More and more women can be seen in the advertisement of kitchen appliances, dishwashing products, washing powders and floor cleaning products, and more men can be seen in advertisements of business, companies, cars and motor bikes with women in background.

Nagi Parul (2014) concludes in her article Projection of Women in Advertisements: a Gender Perception Study that the study concludes that women in print advertisements are depicted as mere sex objects. She also said that women are portrayed in advertisements whether the product is related to them or not. The purchasing behavior of people is affected by the charming women portrayal but this preference varies from person to person. Sometimes people influenced by the charming portrayal of women but most of the time the quality of product can not be confirmed by its portrayal. She suggests that there must either be self regulatory mechanism or government should control the portrayal of women in advertisements.

Patowary Himashree (2014) in her article Portrayal of Women in Indian Mass Media: an Investigation said that media has been ignoring the real problems of women's lives and has been engaged in the negative portrayal of women. The projection of women in Indian media suggests that women are not respected very much in society but often seen as only objects. Women only have three projected roles in media that are biological, domestic and decorative. The author also implies that the sexual objectification of women also leads to violence against women. Women are also often seen as commodities.

Dr. Mishra Deepanjali (2015) in her article Portrayal of Women in Media suggests that the depiction of women in Indian magazines advertisements has been changing. Women are not confined within the four walls of kitchen in these advertisements. Their depiction is now in more modern manner. But the saddest part is that the patriarchal norms still work behind the changed depiction. With modern depiction of women in advertisements, the objectification of women has taken place. Besides being independent and self respecting; women are often portrayed as a sex object in the advertisements.

Dr. Raina Anshu (2014) after analysis different advertisements on Indian television concludes in her article Representation of Indian Women in Advertisements that women are treated as trophy or gift in Indian advertisements which will be given to the person who uses the advertised product. Women are often projected as without any common sense or wit to make decisions. They are very easily attracted or influenced by the person who is using the product being advertised. Such advertisements leave impression on common people's mind that women are very weak and foolish that they can be exploited very easily.

Methodology

This paper is a descriptive study in nature. It is based on secondary information. The secondary data and information have been comprehensively analyzed for preparing this paper. The secondary information have been collected from different scholars' and researchers' published books, articles published in different journals, conference paper, working paper and websites. Some of the advertisements that are running on television now a day are also analyzed to conclude the results.

Portrayal of Women in Indian Television Advertisements

Today, we come across hundreds of advertisements daily. They are affecting every aspect of our day to day dealings, our conversations, our thoughts and to a certain extent control our behavior as customers and consumers. Advertisements stare and scream at us from every street corner, every newspaper, every magazine, every hoarding, every stall or shop or showroom, radio and television. They don't even spare our computer screens when all we are interested in is checking our mail or even simply browsing through.

Advertisement educates people about new products and their uses. Advertising message about the utility of a product enables the people to widen their knowledge. It is advertising which has helped people adopting new ways of life and giving-up old habits. It has contributed to the betterment of the standard of living of the society. But there is another concern about the advertisements that advertisers are using advertisements to sell their product without taking into consideration the negative effects of the content they use in their advertisements. Advertisements has been accused by many feminists of using women in ways that had adverse effects on women's identity in the eyes of world as well as in the eyes of women themselves.

Objectification of Women's Body

Advertisements have long been accused of objectification of women's body for the purpose of selling their products. Feminists have always been opposing advertisements that objectify women's body in any manner. Sometimes women are used in advertisements as a piece of decoration, sometimes advertisers use women to attract the audience specifically male audience. Irrespective of the fact that women are needed or not in any advertisement, they are casted by advertisers just to attract the audience. From 2012, advertisements of Slice Soft Drink started running on television that has one of the most famous actresses of Indian Film Industry Katrina Kaif. Slice has launched many advertisements casting Katrina Kaif and in every advertisement the portrayal of her body can catch attention of anyone. The Slice advertisements with tag line "Ab Ras Barsega" (juice will shower) starts with the view of room in which the lead female is sitting in the window watching a mango tree outside. She stands up and goes to the mirror and put off her bangles while her back is in the full angle of camera with a thin strap showing her back from neck to the end of her spine. While putting her bangles off she has visions of eating mango and the camera start focusing her lips and neck. Then she starts running towards the mango tree while in the background the music is playing with lyrics "Bohot Hui Ye Aankh Micholi, Khelungi Main Ras Ki Holi" (no more hide & seek, m going to play with juice). Then she plucks a mango from the tree with her chunri and starts enjoying the mango and again the angles of camera is in such manner that it is only focusing on her lips, only then a bottle of Slice appeared in her hands.

This advertisement is only one example of many advertisements of Slice Soft Drink portraying women's body in same manner and sometimes even worse. In this particular advertisement in which a soft drink is being advertised, why there was a need to show a woman in such short dress that more than her

half back was open, she was licking her own lip and showing her body. The objectification of women's body has always an issue in the society often raised by different feminists, but the portrayal of women mere as an object to attract the audience is still a trend in the media and in this case in advertisements. In this particular advertisement the kind of dress she is wearing, the kind of postures she is giving are clearly leads to the objectification of women's body. The taste and quality of a soft drink and women's body are not remotely connected to each other but Slice advertisers used a woman and her body to sell their drink.

In advertisements women are used by advertisers to sell their products but many times this usage has many negative impacts on the lives of women. Many advertisements has accused of objectify women's body. Sometimes women are used to sell the products that are not even related to them. For example in the advertisements of men's talcum powder what is the need of women. In addition the portrayal of women in such advertisements is so negative that they are directly harmful for the image of women in the society. In the advertisements of Zatak Men's Talcum Powder, the objectification of women's body is very clear. The advertisement starts with the view of a tailor's shop where the Master Ji (head of the shop) is sitting in the shop and a boy is applying the Zatak Talcum Powder. Then a lady came in traditional India dress that is Saree. The Master Ji calls the boy and asks him to take measurements of the lady. Then the boy came with inches' tape and starts measuring. The moment he touches the belly of the lady, she feels an ice cube slipping on her belly. Then he measures her chest and his hand touches her back and the same ice cube things happened again. The boy who was hesitating in measuring the lady suddenly starts enjoying and continues measuring her neck while in the back ground the song is playing with lyrics "Tere Chhoone Se Thanda Lagne Laga Hai" (I feel cold when

you touch me). The boy and lady were so much enjoying the touch of each other that they both did not notice that the boy has started measuring parts that are not needed but Master Ji notices and the advertisement ends with the tagline "Just Zatak Her".

In this advertisement two main issues can be raised. First of all why do we need women in the advertisement of men's talcum powder and second if we use women anyway, why there is a need to portray her in such a manner that only her body parts becomes the central piece of advertisement and catches all the attention of audience. In this very advertisement, the scene of ice cube running through her body because his hand touches her is very fake and unrealistic. The lady was so much lost in that, that she did not notice that the boy is touching her body parts and reason behind this was only the talcum powder that was being advertised. What message is passes to the general audience, what image of women it creates in the eyes of people, can any woman be so blindly attractive towards an unknown person, these are some of many questions that can be asked to the advertisers of such advertisements. The meaning of the narration "Just Zatak Her" can be interpreted as 'just attack her' or may be make a woman so vulnerable through the touch that she losses her senses to him. Same issue has been raised by many feminists and the campaign was so strong that this advertisement got banned on television but before that it has run through many times that every regular viewer of television has watched it enough times to have a image of that in their minds. Even after the camping against this advertisement, the objectification of women's body is well known and can easily be noticed in other advertisements running on Indian television. The concept of 'male gaze' is important in understanding the portrayal of women as sex objects in advertisements. The advertisers often depict women's image as some decorative piece or center for attraction for the consumers. As men are the main consumers in the society,

they are seen as invisible spectators who define beauty or perfect female body. To please men's gaze, advertisers often portray women's half nude images, more importantly perfectly sized women (Valdivia, Angharad N.).

The objectification of women's body in the advertisements of soup is very common. Though there has been concern among feminists about this issue but the objectification of women's body is still can be seen in almost every advertisement of soup. Very often women are portrayed taking shower, laying in bath tub where half of their body is visible on the screen. In the advertisements of Fiamia Di Wills Soup, one of the successful Bollywood actresses Dipika Padukone has portrayed. The advertisement starts with Dipika smelling a peach in the market place that reminds her Fiamia Di Wills Soup and suddenly she starts running while throwing her bag. On her to home she also took her jacket off and even her sandals before reaching home. The background music is playing the whole time with lyrics "Ab Rukna Mana Hai" (it is forbidden to stop now). She reached home and starts taking bath. She is portrayed laying in bath tub and enjoying the fragrance of the soup, while her body parts have all the focus of the camera. The advertisement does not end here, when she came out of her bath tub, a male (seems to be her partner) entered with another color's Fiamia Di Wills Soup and again she starts jumping on him and few seconds later the advertisement ends with the view of both of them taking shower together with the tag line "Rukna Mana Hai" (it is forbidden to stop).

In another advertisement of soup, the same objectification of women's body is the issue. The advertisement belongs to the company Lux. In a particular advertisement of Lux Bathing Soup, a Bollywood actress Kareena Kapoor has featured. The advertisement focused on the fragrance of the soup. This advertisement starts with Kareena Kapoor walking in a hall while she is putting off her

jewelry and gown with her own voice running in the background, saying "What is Beauty: This- Putting Off Her Ear Ring; This- Putting of Her Necklace ; No, My Beauty is My Confidence, My Perfume- Putting Off Her Gown". Then she is portrayed laying in a bath tub revealing half of her body parts. While she was laying in the bath tub she was projected as if she was laying under the flowers. After that she is shown walking towards the stage and everyone is admiring the fragrance coming out of her. Then the advertisement ends with her saying "The Mystery of Beauty is Lux Perfume".

These two advertisements are just example of hundreds of advertisements of soups that portray women in same manner. The body of women has been used by advertisers to sell their products. Other than the objectification of women's body, advertisements of this kind can also be pointed out for reasons such as they put over emphasis on the beauty of women. In such advertisements women are portrayed with flawless fair skin and slim body, and many times Bollywood divas are projected to set the standards of beauty of women. Through such depictions, women who do not have fair skin or perfectly slim body feel inferior and try to join the race of being fair and slim. For the sole purpose of selling their products, advertisers use fair skin of women without considering the fact that this portrayal can be harmful for women with dark skin tone. Women who cannot fit into that perfect figure not only feel inferior but also this may damage their self confidence.

Findings

After analysis different segments of advertisements from Indian television it can easily be said that feminists have not been wrongly opposing the portrayal of women in advertisements. The projection of women in Indian television advertisements has been affecting the lives of women in different manner. Simon de Beauvoir's concept of

women as “other” to men has successfully been carrying out by the Indian advertisements.

When the country is following the footsteps of globalization and trying to promote the marginalized section of the society through various policies and legislations, women in advertisements are either depicted as sex objects of or a piece of decoration to increase sells of the product. Women have been projecting in advertisements of products that are not connected to them even remotely. Today, violence against women is already growing with high speed, and with the objectification of women as sex objects through these advertisements, the men psyche that women are mere objects and can be used as per their needs, continues to be reinforced. In recent years a new image of women has emerged who is selfish, actively aggressive, sexist, abusive, insensitive, etc. but the main problem is when we notice that this new image can only be seen in advertisements of male deodorants. Media is creating a new false image of women that has no relation with reality. One another very misleading concept of Indian television advertisements is the emphasis on women’s beauty. Advertisements of beauty creams put great pressure on young girls to look like those beauty queens. One of the worst consequences of this is the low self esteem of those women who cannot fit into this unrealistic boundary about the facial beauty. Women with dark complexion spend more and more time and energy to look a bit fairer.

Conclusion

Advertisement is a very powerful tool of media which affects the mind set of people in a very short period of time. In today’s world, women are equally participating with men in almost every field. In mass media, women today have more space than ever before. In advertisements also, now women can be seen much more than men. Advertisements have tendency to carry out a story in one or sometimes even in half minute that leave a

great impression on viewers’ mind because of short and very loud messages they carry. But after close analysis of Indian television advertisements it can be concluded that advertisements in India are not fulfilling their duty towards the society. The projection of women in Indian advertisements that can be done for highlighting the real issues of women’s lives, for their upliftment, for the awareness among people about the rights of women, for the empowerment of women etc. But the focus of advertisers is on something else; their main object is to grow sells of their products without taking into consideration the message any particular advertisement brings to the society. Women very often are used as a piece of decoration in the advertisements for the products that are not connected to them such as men’s deodorants or undergarments. One factor behind the violence against women is the portrayal of women as only sex objects in advertisements.

On the basis of conclusion the following suggestions are made:

- Advertisers should understand that the projection of women in advertisements affects the lives of women and they can sell their products with casting women in stereotypical roles.
- The false depiction of women’s sexuality should be banned on television.
- Women should be casted in advertisements of products that are related to them not just a piece of decoration to attract the audience.
- The objectification of women’s body in advertisements needs to be examined by authorities. The advertisers need to understand the harms that objectification of women’s body can bring to society specifically to women.
- The over emphasis on the outer beauty of women should stop and advertisements of beauty creams should not show women with dark skin color as inferior to others or being rejected because they are not fairer.
- The Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act 1986 should be implemented in more effective manner. Every advertisement in India that cast women should go through the analysis under the sections of this Act.

Bibliography

- Thornham, Sue. (2007) Women Feminism and Media. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- Valdivia, Angharad N. Ed. (2004) A Companion to Media Studies. New Delhi: Atlantic Publisher.
- Prasad, Kiran Ed. (2006) Women, Globalization and Mass Media. Delhi: The Women Press.
- Perse, Elizabeth M. (2001) Media Effects and Society. Mahwah: Lawrence Erlbaum Associate Publications.
- Nagi Parul (2014) Projection of Women in Advertisements: A Gender Perception Study. International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research.
- Dr. Raina Anshu (2014), Representation of Indian Women in Advertisements, Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science.
- Dr. Mishra Deepanjali (2015), Portrayal of Women in Media. Journal of Higher Education and Research Society: A Refereed International.
- Patowary Himashree (2014), Portrayal of Women in Indian Mass Media: An Investigation. Journal of Education and Social Policy.

AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION OF THE CRIMES AGAINST WOMEN IN INDIA

Jasneek Arora

Phd Scholar in Amity University

Under Supervision of Prof. (Dr.) Shalini Singh Sharma

Delegation to the 2nd International Women's Rights Assembly
(Regd: 12IWRA2)

Abstract:

Violation of women rights, their safety, integrity and dignity have been the key features of the Indian society for the past two decades. Women, who form nearly 48% of the population of India (Census 2011), are the victims of major form of crimes. Crime against women in India is linked to their disadvantageous position in the society. Where women empowerment is a key to sustainable development and prolonged economic growth, crime against women act as a significant barrier to their growth and development. Therefore, an attempt has been made to empirically investigate the relationship between growth and women rights at all India level with some of the most severe form of crimes against women (rape, kidnapping and abduction, outrage of women's modesty, cruelty by husband, dowry deaths, and insult to the modesty of women). The two dominant explanatory variables of growth and women rights being GDP and literacy ratio. The paper also focuses on inter-state variations of per female crime against women. The investigation has been done for the period 2001-2014. The data has been retrieved from National Crime Records Bureau, Central Statistical Organization and Census of India.

Keywords: *Advertisement, Gender, Objectification, Patriarchy, Stereotyping.*

Women form 48.5% of the population of India, but are still oppressed and suppressed in various spheres and are the victims of major form of crimes. Various developing societies with gender discrimination, such as of India, face obstruction in socio-economic progress of the nation, in turn, hindering the development of the nation in fields of poverty eradication, labour force participation, education and skill development, job creation, health etc. (Anant, 2015) Social evils such as violence against women and non-accessibility to the judicial system are hurdles for a nation to achieve the path of self reliance. Crime against women add to their disadvantageous position in the society, further acting as a significant barrier to their as well as to the country's growth. (Tjaden & Thoennes,

1998) crime against women came to be viewed as a serious problem because of re-emergence of Women's Movement. (UNIFEM, 2003) Secretary General of United Nations, view violence against women as universal and the most shameful representation of human rights. Violation of women rights, their safety and integrity have been the key features of the Indian society for the past two decades. (Heise et al., 1999) one woman in every three around the world has been beaten, forced to sex or abused in her life. Crimes against women in India are increasing at startling rate. An increase of 1, 94,127 cases of total crimes against women were reported at All India level in 2001 over 2014.

Much of the literature from fields of philosophy, law, sociology has examined

violence against women in the context of feminist ideology. Despite outnumbered research in the dimension of crime against women particularly in the areas of domestic violence and rape, many of the areas are yet to be explored. One reason for lack of research in this domain might be the paucity of data for criminal activity.

Crime against women in India:

Crime or violence against women is recognised as a major health concern affecting her mental and physical health. Violence against women includes sexual, physical, psychological and economic abuse. Patriarchal society as one of India where culture have beliefs and norms that perpetuate violence against women, is on the verge of becoming demographic dividend power, where a crime against women is recorded every 1.7 minute; every 16 minutes a rape case is recorded and every 4.4 minutes a girl or a woman is subjected to domestic violence (FCRA). Although women are victims of general crimes such as murder, theft, cheating etc., yet the crimes directed specifically to women are known as crime against women (National Crime Records Bureau). Crime in India is an annual publication by National Crime Records bureau. Under the criminal procedure code crime is differentiated in two heads: cognizable and non-cognizable crimes. Cognizable crimes are the ones where police investigates without the permission of magistrate and arrests without warrant. Cognizable crimes are further divided into Indian penal code (IPC) and Special and local laws (SLL). Non-cognizable crimes are the one where parties affected are dealt in court and the police needs permission of the magistrate for investigation. This paper explores different types of crimes against women under the IPC section, namely; rape, kidnapping and abduction, assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty, insult to the modesty of a woman, dowry deaths, cruelty by husband or his relatives and total crimes against women.

The All India crime rate under crime against women i.e., number of crimes per lakh population, increased by 42.3 crimes from 2001 to 2014. Mizoram reported the highest crime rate of 23.7 crimes followed by New Delhi at 23.2 crimes. This increase in crime rate brings out a gloomy and abused picture of Indian women. Until now, empirical estimation on the relationship between crimes against women and economic growth and development has been scarce. Therefore, the paper makes an attempt to study the relationship between various types of crimes against women and economic growth and development. Gross domestic product and literacy ratio are the key proxy variables for economic growth and development respectively. The investigation has been done for the period 2001-2014. The data has been retrieved from National Crime Records Bureau, National Sample Survey Organisation, Census of India and Central Statistical Organisation.

Trends in crime against women for the period 2001-2014 (Figures are presented in Appendix section):

This section deals with trend analysis of various crimes against women along with their conceptualisation. The crime head wise details of crime against women from 2001 to 2014 are as follows:

- i. Rape (Section 376, IPC): A man is said to commit a rape who has sexual intercourse with a woman under the following circumstances:
 - (a) Against her will
 - (b) Without her consent
 - (c) With her consent, consent obtained by putting her or any person in fear of death or hurt whom she is interested in
 - (d) With or without her consent when she is under 16 years of age

The “Nirbhaya” incident of 2012 which shook the country brought out the stark reality of crime against women. Yet, the incidence of rapes has been increasing in the country. (Singh & Sandeepa, 2014) there are three aspects of major crime against women one being Rape. An over alarming trend is seen in number of rapes being committed from 2001-2014. There has been an increase of 129% in the incidence of rape. Despite various actions taken by the government to protect women, the incidence of rapes has not stopped yet has increased far further. Looking at the inter-state variations 14% of the cases were reported in Madhya Pradesh followed by Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and Maharashtra (NCRB). These states accounted for 49% of the total rape cases.

- ii. Dowry Deaths (Section 304B, IPC): Dowry death refers to death of a woman caused by any burns or bodily injury occurs within seven years of marriage and it is shown soon before her death she was subjected to any demand for dowry. (Sanghavi et.al,2001) suggested burns are an important public health concern and estimated 106000 out of 163000 fire related deaths occurred in women. Despite the Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961 and various other penalties imposed for demanding or taking dowry. There has been an increase of 29% in the number of dowry deaths from 2001-2014. The highest number of cases of dowry was reported in Uttar Pradesh, which comprise of 29.2% followed by Bihar.
- iii. Kidnapping and Abduction (Section 366, IPC): Whoever kidnaps or abducts any woman with intent that she will be forced to marry against her will or she may be forced to illicit intercourse, shall be punished with imprisonment.

incidence of kidnapping and abduction of women during the past thirteen years. If we see in absolute numbers at All India level the number of kidnapping and abduction cases has increased by 42,666 crimes. Looking at the inter-state variation, Uttar Pradesh accounts for 10,628 cases (NCRB).

- iv. Assault on women to outrage her modesty (Section 354): Whoever assault or uses criminal force to any woman intending to outrage her modesty shall be punished with imprisonment.

The incidence of assault on women to outrage her modesty has increased by 141% from 2001 to 2014. In absolute numbers the crime accounted for an increase of 48,111 cases for the period. Inter-state variations reveal that Maharashtra has the highest number of incidences followed by Madhya Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh. Delhi (UT) has the highest crime rate (47.9) of assault on women outraging her modesty.

- v. Insult to the modesty of women (Section 509): Anyone intending to insult the modesty of any woman by uttering any word or making any gesture or sound, or anything which intrudes the privacy of a woman, shall be punished with imprisonment.

There has been a positive change in the incidence of insult to the modesty of women crimes, and the cases have been reduced by 0.11%. The crime cases have been reduced by 29.3% as compared to the previous year, 2013. However, the inter-state variations report that Andhra Pradesh followed by Maharashtra have the highest incidences of such crime. Most of the cases of this nature took place at places of work and of public transport.

It is a very disturbing picture to see that there has been an increase of 291% in the

vi. Cruelty by husband or his relatives (Section 498a, IPC): Whoever being the husband or relative of the husband of woman, subjects such woman to cruelty, where cruelty meaning harassment of woman or any wilful conduct driving the woman to commit suicide or to cause any injury or danger to life, limb and health shall be punished with imprisonment.

(Krantz & Moreno, 2005) estimated that 40%-52% of women in USA and Mexico experience physical violence by an intimate partner and have also been sexually coerced. (Jeyaseelan et.al, 2007) carried a survey of 9938 women in India, and found that quarter of women reported experience of violent physical behaviour by the husband. An increase of 150% is seen for the defined period in cases of cruelty by husband or relatives. Highest number of cases was reported in West Bengal, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and Assam.

vii. The total crimes against women under the Indian Penal code have increased by 135% for the period 2001 to 2014. This increase in crime against women sets a worrying situation in a developing nation like India. If the crimes against women continue to grow at such a riding phase then the

Data analysis:

Crime in India deals with various types of crime against women under Indian Penal Code. Seven set of equations were estimated at all India level which covers specific crime against women in all Indian states as well as total crime against women in all the states. The section raises the question whether crime against women in India can be explained by the growth rate, literacy rate of all of the population and sex ratio. In order to examine this hypothesis we estimated, using all India level data, seven econometric

equations whose dependent variables were, respectively, the number of crime against women at all India level: (1) rape; (2) kidnapping and abduction; (3) assault on women to outrage her modesty; (4) cruelty by husband or his relatives; (5) insult to the modesty of women; (6) dowry deaths and (7) total crime against women. The equations were estimated as a system of (Zellner, 1962) Seemingly Unrelated Regression Equations (SURE).

A. Crime as a function:

The hypothesis is that crimes against women depend upon socio-economic variables. The variables are structured as follows:

- (a) Economic Growth: Gross domestic product at constant prices (2004-05) published by CSO has been used in this paper as a measure of economic growth. (Kumar, 2013) establishes the causality between crime rates and economic growth. The Global Peace Index Report 2013 ranks India in the category of 25 most violent countries that loses 4 percent of its GDP due to criminal activity in 2012.
- (b) Education: education attainment increases the success ratio of entering into labour market, by learning various skills. Education therefore, (Freeman, 1991; Groger, 1995) increases the opportunity cost of criminal activity. Literacy rate of population is used in this paper as a proxy for education attainment available at Census of India.
- (c) Sex Ratio: criminal activity especially against women increases on account of higher male to female ratio. This ratio explains inequality present in the society. Therefore, sex ratio that is number of females per 1000 males has been used as an indicator of inequality.

B. Crime as a model:

The SURE model which we have used comprises of M multiple regression equations:

$$y_{ti} = \sum_{j=1}^{K_i} x_{tij} \beta_{ij} + u_{ti}$$

Where y_{ti} is the t^{th} observation on the i^{th} dependent variable; x_{tij} is the t^{th} observation on the j^{th} explanatory variable appearing on the i^{th} equation; β_{ij} is the coefficient associated with x_{tij} at each observation and u_{ti} is the t^{th} value of the random disturbance term associated with the i^{th} equation of the model.

In matrix notation, this model is expressed as:

$$y_i = X_i \beta_i + u_i \quad (i = 1, \dots, M)$$

Writing this equation as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_M \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & X_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & X_M \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \\ \beta_M \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_M \end{bmatrix}$$

The results of the analysis are shown in Table 1.

The present analysis reveals that there is an increase in crimes related to rape, kidnapping and abduction, dowry deaths, assault on women to outrage her modesty and cruelty by husband or his relatives in India during 2001-2014. Inter-state variations reveal that majority of the crimes occurred in north western parts of India viz., Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh and Maharashtra.

The regression analysis indicates that rape, kidnapping and abduction, assault on women to outrage her modesty have an inverse relationship with GDP, since all three

coefficients are negative. This implies that as the economy prospers or grows the crimes will decrease. That is, if GDP increases these three crimes in numbers will decrease. Insult to the modesty of women has an inverse relationship with literacy rates, implying, the more educated members in a society the lesser the crime related to insult of a woman's modesty. Cruelty by husband or relatives and insult to the modesty of women have an inverse relationship with sex ratio, as the number of females rise per 1000 males these two crimes will fall. Looking at all the seven regression equations the results related to significance of the variables can be summed up as follows:

- Rape: literacy rate is found to be significant to 95% confidence level. The amount of variance in the data which is shown by R^2 is found to be very low at 33.8%.
- Kidnapping and Abduction: literacy rate is statistically significant at 1% level of significance. The variance shown by the equation is 50%. That is half of the variance in the data, i.e.; the influence on crime is described in the regression equation.
- Assault on women to outrage her modesty: all the explanatory variables are found to insignificant. The variance explained by the regression equation is very low at 25%
- Cruelty by husband or relatives: literacy rate is found to be highly significant at 1% level of confidence. The amount of variance shown in the regression equation is 58%, which is a good sign. This implies, around 60% of the changes in this crime can be influence by all the three explanatory variables. The regression equation is also found to be significant within a 95% confidence level in the F test.
- Dowry Deaths: GDP stands out to be statistically significant within 95% level

of confidence and the variable literacy rate significant within 90% level of confidence. 66.5% level of variation is shown in the regression equation. The equation is also found to be significant within a 99% level in the F test.

- (f) Insult to the modesty of a woman: the explanatory variables are insignificant at all the three confidence interval with level of variation shown in the regression equation very low at 33%.
- (g) Total crimes against women: the variance shown by the equation 41%. That is 60 per cent of the variance in the data i.e., the influence on crime is not describes in the regression equation. Only literacy rate is found to be significant within 95% level of confidence.

The coefficient of GDP is found to be statistically insignificant for most of the crimes except Dowry deaths and for sex ratio insignificant associations is seen for all the crimes. The value of R^2 is very low for rape, assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty, insult to the modesty of women and total crimes against women suggesting that important independent variables were not included in the regression equation. This leads us to questioning the validity of the data. Confounding factors, such as under reporting may be distorting the analysis. The data for crime against women cannot be expected to truly signify the prevalence of violence against women in India. Much of the data goes unreported due to lack of knowledge, voice and support. The general public tolerance is also a factor contributing to the data being under reported. Thus, it is not at all surprising to see that the regression results for most of the crimes against women across India yield insignificant results.

The results, therefore, show that economic growth and development has an important effect on crime against women across India. It does not; however rule out the possibility of including other important explanatory factors such as crime cases solved by police,

age of women and other economic, legal and social factors of macroeconomic as well as microeconomic nature in determining crime against women. the evidence presented, induces to take steps and formulate policies for curbing violence against women; such as; changing our attitude towards violence against women, improving transport facilities for women, reservation of seats for women in police force, centres for women affected by violence etc. (Kumar & Kumar, 2013) an effective measure to control crime is to ensure increase in density of police and per capita availability of police. Moreover, an economic and social inclusive development prevents the occurrence of crime against women. Kerala has the least number of crime against women as it has highest female to male ratio.

Conclusion:

Violence against women is a complex economic and social problem. Much of the literature worldwide is focussing on this issue as how to address crime against women. Addressing the issue requires coordination between nations, communities and different development sectors of the economy such as education, health to challenge the customs and norms that lead to rising inequalities and violence against women. The results from our all level India analysis provide strong evidence in favour robust economic growth and strong educational base for curbing crime against women. The results show that increase in GDP, literacy rate and sex ratio will decrease crime against women. Thus, there is a need for coming up with policies to establish a system to change the attitudes of criminals through education or imparting vocational training. Nothing works better than self help, women, therefore, must get training in self prevention at institutional as well as at individual level.

Result of this paper show that economic development gauged by literacy rate, in particular, is an important determinant of

crime rates. The reform process has led to spur in the growth and development process, yet, there is a need for a participatory approach in combating crimes against women.

References:

- Zellner, A. (1962). An efficient method of estimating seemingly unrelated regressions and tests for aggregation bias. *Journal of the American statistical association*, 57(298), 348-368
- Tjaden, P., & Thoennes, N. (1998). Prevalence, Incidence and Consequences of violence against women: Findings from National Violence against women survey. *ERIC*
- Heise, L., Ellsberg, M., & Gottemoeller, M., (1999). Ending violence against women. *Population reports*, 27(4), 1-1
- Dreze, J., & Reetika, K., (2000). Crime, gender and society in India: insights from homicide data. *Population and Development Review*, 26(2), 335-352
- Hackett, M., (2001). Domestic violence against women: statistical analysis of crimes across India. *Journal of Comparative Family Studies*
- Nayak, M., Byrne, C., Martin, M., & Abraham, A., (2003). Attitude towards violence against women: a cross nation study. *Sex Role*, Vol. 49, Nos. 7/8
- Krantz, G., & Garcia-Moreno, C., (2005). Violence against women. *Journal of epidemiology and community health*, 59(10), 818-821.
- Ahmed, S., & Jejeebhoy, S., (2006). Individual and Contextual determinants of domestic violence in North India. *American Journal of Public Health*
- Jeyaseelan, L., Kumar, S., Neelakantan, N., Peedicayil, A., Pillai, R., & Duvury, N. (2007). Physical spousal violence against women in India: some risk factors. *Journal of biosocial science*, 39(05), 657-670
- Sanghavi, P., Bhalla, K., & Das, V., (2009). Fire related deaths in India in 2001: a retrospective analysis of data. *The Lancet*, 373(9671), 1282-1288
- Flood, M., & Pease, B., (2009). Factors influencing attitudes to violence against women. *Trauma, Violence & Abuse*, Vol.10, No.2, 125-142
- Detotto, C., & Otranto, E. (2010). Does crime affect economic growth? *Kyklos (international review for social sciences)*, 63(3), 330-345.
- Morgan, K., (2011). Inequality and Crime. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 82 (4): 530-539
- Babu, G., & Babu, B., (2011). Dowry deaths: a neglected public health issue in India. *International Health*, 3, 35-43
- Mishra, A., & Patel, A., (2013). Crimes against the elderly in India: a content analysis on factors causing fear of crime. *International Journal of Criminal Justice Sciences*, Vol.8
- Kumar, S., (2013). Crime and economic growth: evidence from India. *Munich Personal RePEc Archive*
- Mishra, A. (2015) Combating gender based violence: Achieving gender equality in post 2015. *Journal of Social Sciences*, Vol. 2, Issue 2

MAJOR ISSUES & CHALLENGES OF WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Maya Ravindran
Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of Sociology Annamalai
University, Annamalai Nagar
Under Supervision of Dr. J. Nagaraj

Delegation to the 2nd International Women's Rights Assembly
(Regd: 02IWRA2)

Abstract:

The term “Women Empowerment” which is basically a process of creation of an environment where women can think and grow independently and make their own decisions on their personal development and contribute their best to the development of the society. In the past few decades, we have succeeded in removing the psychological barrier of mostly male dominated society and women now have been flourishing at great pace and making their presence felt in all spheres of life; social, economical, political and in the scientific advancement as well. The women CEO's of India's top most companies and presence of Indian women in Forbes Most Influential Women list indicates the ascendance of Indian women on higher ladder of achievement culminating into Empowered Women. There is no denying the fact that education has played a vital role in ameliorating the status of women. From the chair person of Indian Parliament to the distinguished judges of Supreme Court of India, remarkable changes in the positions of women could be noticeable. However, great variations in the positions of women still exist at every nook and corner of the country. The researchers underline the fact that only a marginal section of the society has been empowered while those belonging to the lower middle class and to the rural areas are deprived of their share in the development process. In this regard, this paper aims to review the major issues & challenges of women empowerment.

Keywords: *Women, Empowerment, Human Rights, Violence*

Women have generally been looked upon with contempt for centuries with various strictures inflicted upon them reducing their status to the mercy of men. They have been confined to hearth and home. But now the perspective of the society has changed and a general thinking to work for the emancipation and empowerment of women is being developed so that they could also contribute in the enhancement and welfare of the society.

A woman's empowerment begins with consciousness—perceptions about herself and her rights, her capabilities and her potentials, awareness of how gender and

socio-cultural and political forces affect her. Political empowerment, economic development and social upliftment of women are necessary and desirable to fight myriad forms of patriarchal domination, and discrimination at every stage. In fact, women's empowerment is central to the achievement of the triple goals of equality, development and social justice. And for that political participation is needed.

In a democratic system, women participation may be viewed at two levels:

(i) Awareness and assertion of women political rights;

(ii) Acquisition and exercise of power.

Twentieth Century has brought a great change in the life of women all over world and 21st Century is the century of women. Woman's attitudes, values, inspirations, ways of feelings, standards of behaviour and acting for effective participation in all walks of life are becoming reality. Rays of hope are becoming brighter and radical changes in and through women's thrust in socio-economic and political process, will be instrumental to healthier, happier and progressive state in near future. As the largest vibrant democracy in the world, India has been continuously experimenting with a number of forms and modes of organizations and structures to achieve gender equality. Even then gender bias and discrimination at every stage show, what kind of society women have to live in. One can just think, the way the girls and boys grow up in their childhood.

Women Emancipation

But their emancipation is not without challenges. Breaking the age old barriers, storming into a predominantly male bastion are something they have to fight for. Even as they are becoming aware about their rights and demands, the violence and crime against women is on the increase. History is the witness that the women had enjoyed a privileged position in ancient India. It is definitely a matter of pride that there existed a culture and them a respectful Living in the social life. However, the woman lost their status with the coming up of Brahminical traditions and with the advent of Islam, they were further pushed into the background. They were left secluded, devitalized and sheltered and these practices slowly turned into customs which have now become traditions.

A new chapter was added into the history of women's empowerment with India gaining independence. The norm of their less, unimportant of secondary role to that of men was withdrawn. When the new constitution

was formed, the constitution makers took into account the Women's plight and asserted by introducing various measures in the constitution to hold their rightful place in the society. They were given freedom to participate in the social, political, economic and cultural life of the nation.

Feminism Movement

During 1960s and 1970s the movement by the women to seek equality with men gained ground all over the world. With this movement called feminism, the educated women in particular and poor rural women in general realized the need to break the old shackles to breathe in the open space. Still the experience shows that man's tyrannical hegemony is overwhelmingly strong and deep rooted to allow for any change in the short run. In India a crime is committed against a woman every seven minutes. Every 26 minutes a molestation take place and every 54 minute somewhere a woman is raped. The burning of brides for dowry continues unabated in the various parts of the country.

The condition of rural women is still more deplorable. The various women's movements are led and organised by white collared middle class women and social workers from upper and upper middle class non-working women who are unaware about the ground realities existing in the rural structure of Indian society and are not concerned to the rural women's miserable conditions. Women's organization has lobbied heavily for the introduction of Women Reservation Bill for 33 per cent reservation in Lok Sabha and in state assembly seats.

In the Panchayats and municipalities the reservation has already been provided. They have said that the reservations would give them political platform to work for the rest of women for their emancipation. The government has also taken various measures like committee on statues of women in 1974, followed by National Plan of Action for

women and the National Perspective Plan for women in 1988.

However despite of these measures, the challenges before the women for their emancipation has remained still an uphill task and their conditions still remained the same. What is required is the seriousness of the various government agencies to work for the women's empowerment by spreading awareness through various educative programmes.

An expert group meeting on Equality in Political Participation and Decision-making organized by DAW made the following recommendations to women's status in political parties: ??As an interim measure, substantial targets, such as quotas or similar forms of positive action to ensure; Women's candidacy for office and participation in political posts should be applied;

- Training programmes should be developed to increase the political and management skills of women in politics, both as candidates and as elected or appointed officials, especially making use of the experience of other women who have achieved public office.
- Women's sections of parties should be evaluated and strengthened to enable them to influence party policy and promote female candidacy.
- Information on potential women candidates should be compiled, maintained on a systematic basis and made available when candidacy or appointments are considered.
- Parties should be encouraged to examine the criteria used to select persons for political functions to ensure that the varieties of experience possessed by women are taken into account in selection.
- Training activities should be developed to sensitize party members to the needs and potentials of female members.

- As an interim measure where the electoral system might make it useful, parties should undertake special measures to provide funding for women candidates for office.

Other important mechanisms include networking, participation in the campaigns of other politicians, lobbying, and membership in the same clubs, professional and academic associations. The corrective mechanisms are to be viewed holistically and not as isolated piecemeal actions. Only then the women will be at par with men in all fields.

Concept of Empowerment

Empowerment refers to policies and measures designed to increase the degree of autonomy and self-determination in the lives of people and in communities in order to enable them to represent their interests in a responsible and self-determined way, acting (again) on their own authority. Empowerment refers both to the process of self-empowerment and to professional support of people, which enables them to overcome their sense of powerlessness and lack of influence, and to recognize and eventually use their resources and chances.

Empowerment is a multi-dimensional process, which should enable women or group of women to realize their full identity and power in all spheres of life. It consists of greater access to knowledge and resources, greater autonomy in decision making to enable them to have greater ability to plan their lives, or to have greater control over the circumstances that influence their lives and free from shocks imposed on them by custom, belief and practice. Generally development with justice is expected to generate the forces that lead to empowerment of various sections of population in a country and to raise their status especially in case of women. "Empowerment comes from Women's groups who seek to empower themselves through greater self-reliance. They have right to determine their own

choices in life. They also seek to gain control and access to resources". Empowerment is process, which helps people to gain control of their lives through raising awareness, taking action and working in order to exercise greater control.

It often involves the empowered developing confidence in their own capacities. Empowerment is probably the totality of the following or similar capabilities:

1. Having decision-making power of their own
2. Having access to information and resources for taking proper decision
3. Having a range of options from which you can make choices
4. Ability to exercise assertiveness in collective decision making
5. Having positive thinking on the ability to make change
6. Ability to learn skills for improving one's personal or group power.
7. Ability to change others' perceptions by democratic means.
8. Involving in the growth process and changes that is never ending and self-initiated
9. Increasing one's positive self-image and overcoming stigma

Issues and Problems faced by Women in India

There are various issues and problems which women generally face in the society in India. Some of the problems are mentioned and described below:

1. **Selective abortion and female infanticide:** It is the most common practice for years in India in which abortion of female fetus is performed in the womb of mother after the fetal sex determination and sex selective abortion by the medical professionals.

2. **Sexual harassment:** It is the form of sexual exploitation of a girl child at home,

streets, public places, transports, offices, etc by the family members, neighbors, friends or relatives.

3. **Dowry and Bride burning:** It is another problem generally faced by women of low or middle class family during or after the marriage. Parents of boys demand a lot of money from the bride's family to be rich in one time. Groom's family perform bride burning in case of lack of fulfilled dowry demand. In 2005, around 6787 dowry death cases were registered in India according to the Indian National Crime Bureau reports.

4. **Disparity in education:** The level of women education is less than men still in the modern age. Female illiteracy rate higher in the rural areas. Where over 63% or more women remain unlettered.

5. **Domestic violence:** it is like endemic and widespread disease affects almost 70% of Indian women according to the women and child development official. It is performed by the husband, relative or other family member.

6. **Child Marriages:** Early marriage of the girls by their parents in order to be escaped from dowry. It is highly practiced in the rural India.

7. **Inadequate Nutrition:** Inadequate nutrition in the childhood affects women in their later life especially women belonging to the lower middle class and poor families.

8. **Low status in the family:** It is the abuse or violence against women. Women are considered as inferior to men so they are not allowed to join military services.

9. **Status of widows:** Widows are considered as worthless in the Indian society. They are treated poorly and forced to wear white clothes.

Earlier women were facing problems like child marriage, sati pratha, pardapratha, restriction to widow remarriage, widows' exploitation, devadasi system, etc. However, almost all the old traditional problems have been disappeared gradually from the society but given rise to other

Need for Women Empowerment

Reflecting into the "Vedas Purana" of Indian culture, women are being worshiped such as LAXMI MAA, goddess of wealth; SARSWATI MAA, for wisdom; DURGA MAA for power. The status of women in India particularly in rural areas needs to address the issue of empowering women. About 66% of the female population in rural area is unutilized. This is mainly due to existing social customs. In agriculture and Animal care the women contribute 90% of the total workforce. Women constitute almost half of the population, perform nearly 2/3 of its work hours, receive 1/10th of the world's income and own less than 1/ 100th the world property. Among the world's 900 million illiterate people, women out number men two to one. 70% of people living in poverty are women. Lower sex ratio (i.e.) 933, the existing studies show that the women are relatively less healthy than men though belong to same class. They constitute less than 1/7th of the administrators and mangers in developing countries. Only 10% seats in World Parliament and 6% in National Cabinet are held by women.

Major Ways to Empower Women in Society

- Changes in women's mobility and social interaction
- Changes in women's labour patterns
- Changes in women's access to and control over resources and
- Changes in women's control over Decision making
- Providing education
- Self employment and Self help group

- Providing minimum needs like Nutrition, Health, Sanitation, Housing
- Other than this society should change the mentality towards the word women
- Encouraging women to develop in their fields they are good at and make a career

Schemes for Women Empowerment

The Government programmes for women development began as early as 1954 in India but the actual participation began only in 1974. The efforts of government and its different agencies are ably supplemented by nongovernmental organizations that are playing an equally important role in facilitating women empowerment. Despite concerted efforts of governments and NGOs there are certain gaps. At present, the Government of India has over 34 schemes for women operated by different department and ministries. Some of these are as follows;

1. Rastria Mahila Kosh (RMK) 1992-1993
2. Mahila Samridhi Yojana (MSY) October,1993.
3. Indira Mahila Yojana (IMY) 1995.
4. Women Entrepreneur Development programme given top priority in 1997-98.
5. Mahila Samakhya being implemented in about 9000 villages.
6. Swayasjdha.
7. Swa Shakti Group.
8. Support to Training and Employment Programme for Women(STEP).
9. Swalamban.
10. Crèches/ Day care centre for the children of working and ailing mother.
11. Hostels for working women.
12. Swadhar.
13. National Mission for Empowerment of Women.
14. Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) (1975),
15. Rajiv Gandhi Scheme for Empowerment of Adolescence Girls (RGSEAG) (2010).

16. The Rajiv Gandhi National Crèche Scheme for Children of Working Mothers.
17. Integrated Child Protection scheme (ICPS) (2009-2010).
18. Dhanalakahmi (2008).
19. Short Stay Homes.
20. Ujjawala (2007).
21. Scheme for Gender Budgeting (XI Plan).
22. Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP).
23. Training of Rural Youth for Self Employment (TRYSEM).
24. Prime Minister's Rojgar Yojana (PMRY).
25. Women's Development Corporation Scheme (WDCS).
26. Working Women's Forum.
27. Indira Mahila Kendra.
28. Mahila Samiti Yojana.
29. Khadi and Village Industries Commission.
30. Indira Priyadarahini Yojana.
31. SBI's Sree Shaki Scheme.
32. SIDBI's Mahila Udyam Nidhi Mahila Vikas Nidhi.
33. NGO's Credit Schemes.
34. National Banks for Agriculture and Rural Development's Schemes

Challenges of Women Empowerment

There are several constraints that check the process of women empowerment in India. Social norms and family structure in developing countries like India, manifests and perpetuate the subordinate status of women. One of the norms is the continuing preference for a son over the birth of a girl child which is present in almost all societies and communities. The society is more biased in favor of male child in respect of education, nutrition and other opportunities. The root cause of this type of attitude lies in the belief that male child inherits the clan in India with an exception of Meghalaya. Women often internalize the traditional concept of their role as natural thus inflicting an injustice upon them. Poverty is the reality of life for the vast majority women in India. It is the another factor that poses challenge in realizing women's empowerment. There are

several challenges that are plaguing the issues of women's right in India. Targeting these issues will directly benefit the empowerment of women in India

Education

While the country has grown from leaps and bounds since independence where education is concerned. the gap between women and men is severe. While 82.14% of adult men are educated, only 65.46% of adult women are known to be literate in India. The gender bias is in higher education, specialized professional trainings which hit women very hard in employment and attaining top leadership in any field.

Poverty

Poverty is considered the greatest threat to peace in the world, and eradication of poverty should be a national goal as important as the eradication of illiteracy. Due to this, women are exploited as domestic helps.

Health and Safety

The health and safety concerns of women are paramount for the wellbeing of a country and is an important factor in gauging the empowerment of women in a country. However there are alarming concerns where maternal healthcare is concerned.

Professional Inequality

This inequality is practiced in employment and promotions. Women face countless handicaps in male customized and dominated environs in Government Offices and Private enterprises.

Morality and Inequality

Due to gender bias in health and nutrition there is unusually high morality rate in

women reducing their population further especially in Asia, Africa and china.

Household Inequality

Household relations show gender bias in infinitesimally small but significant manners all across the globe, more so, in India e.g. sharing burden of housework, childcare and menial works by so called division of work.

Empowerment of Women

Active participation of any community in the development process is recognized as a tool for its empowerment. In Indian social set up, the participation of women in the development process has to be ensured through tangible measures taken at various levels for their overall development. The government has taken a conscious view to make adequate provisions in its policies and programmes, through which it is to be ensured that the women of the country are not only empowered but also become active participants in the development process in the country. Various programmes of the Ministry of Rural Development are formulated keeping in view the above perspective.

Ministry of Rural Development is implementing various poverty alleviation and rural development programmes. These programmes have special components for women. Major schemes, having women's component, implemented by the Ministry include the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA), Swarnjayanti Gram warozgar Yojana (SGSY) now restructured as National Rural Livelihood Mission, (Aajeevika) and the Indira Awaas Yojana (IAY). The implementation of these programmes is monitored specifically with reference to coverage of women. But this programme does have a significant impact on the living conditions of the rural women in terms of providing connectivity through the rural

roads, which may enhance the opportunities for the girl child to have an access to the educational facilities. Similarly, due to better rural roads women may have easier access to the health facilities and local market which may not only increase their productivity but may also increase their awareness which goes a long way in changing the traditional social structure and resulting in improvement of the status of the rural women.

Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA):

The MGNREGA guarantees 100 days of employment in a financial year to any rural household whose adult members are willing to do unskilled manual work. It is provided in the Act that while providing employment, priority shall be given to women in such a way that at least one third of the beneficiaries shall be women who have registered and requested for work under the Act.

During the year 2012-13 (up to 27th Dec. 2012) total employment of 134.76 crore person days were reported to have been generated. The employment generated for women were reported as 71.88 crores person days which is 53.34% of total employment generated under this Programme. To increase participation rates of women workers in MGNREGA, the Ministry has suggested that individual bank/post office accounts must compulsorily be opened in the name of all women MGNREGA workers and their wages directly credited to their own account for the number of days worked by them.

This Ministry has also advised the States:

- To identify widowed women, deserted women and destitute women who qualify as a household under the Act, to ensure that they are provided 100 days of work.
- To ensure that pregnant women and lactating mothers (at least up to 8 months before delivery and 10

months after delivery) are given works which require less effort and are close to their houses.

- To conduct time and motion studies to formulate gender, age, level of disability, terrain and climate sensitive Schedule of Rates (SoRs) and to ensure accurate capturing of work done by women at worksites.
- To ensure that at least 50% of the worksite supervisors (mates) at all worksites are women.
- To ensure that worksite facilities such as crèches, drinking water, shade etc. are provided through convergence with Women and Child Development Schemes like ICDS.
- To encourage participation of women groups, including Self Help Groups in awareness generation, capturing demand, planning, implementation, monitoring and maintenance of works. All these suggestions are also incorporated in MGNREGA Operational Guidelines 2013.

National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM):

A Self Help Group (SHG), of 10-20 women in general (5-20 in difficult areas) is the primary building block of the NRLM institutional design. NRLM would promote SHGs with exclusive women membership. The SHGs and the federation of these SHGs at village and higher levels shall serve the purpose of providing women member's space for self-help, mutual cooperation and collective action for social and economic development. NRLM is working with groups of exclusive women membership because it recognizes that women are marginalized in the economy, in polity and in society. Thus, building and sustaining institutions of poor women at various levels would give them social, economic and political empowerment and thereby bring significant qualitative improvement in their lives. NRLM will especially focus on women headed

households, single women, women victim of trafficking, women with disability and other such vulnerable categories.

The following factors define women SHGs under the NRLM:

- They are homogeneous, affinity groups of poor women, who have come together to

Overcome poverty. Membership is voluntary and it consists of only poor women.

- The federations shall have women representatives only from member SHGs and there are clear conditions for admission to the federation and clear norms for remaining as members.
- These are institutions truly owned by poor women, and they really experience 'ownership'.
- They have long term objectives. At least 10 years of continuous and nurturing support is required for a poor woman to come out of abject poverty and stay out of poverty.
- Hence SHGs and their federations need to function for a long period of time to achieve their objectives.
- The SHGs and their federations shall play an active role in taking up social issues affecting their members - issues of domestic violence, alcoholism, girl child marriages, etc. This is one of the hallmarks of a genuine self help movement.

An important component of NRLM is the Mahila Kisan Sashaktikaran Pariyojana (MKSP) which aims at supporting women farmers. Primarily, MKSP aims to recognize women farmers,

Unrecognized category, even though most of the farming activities are almost exclusively handled by the women. MKSP also, inter alia, seeks to reduce drudgery for women Farmers.

they could participate and that targeted gender equality and women's empowerment.

The Indira Awaas Yojana (IAY):

Indira Awaas Yojana is a social welfare flagship programme, created by the Indian Government, to provide housing for the rural poor in India. The differentiation is made between rural poor and urban poor for a separate set of schemes operate for the urban poor (like the Basic Services for Urban Poor). IAY aims at providing assistance for the construction of houses to the people Below the Poverty Line in rural areas. Under the Scheme, priority is extended to widows and unmarried women. It is stipulated that IAY houses are to be allotted in the name of women members of the household or, alternatively, in the joint names of husband and wife.

Conclusion

Productive employment and decent work in developing countries, including in fragile contexts, are the main routes out of poverty for both women and men. Women's participation in the labour market can be increased by addressing the constraints and barriers women face accessing work, including public employment programmes, and by providing well-focused vocational training. Women experience barriers in almost every aspect of work – including: whether they have paid work at all, the type of work they obtain or are excluded from, the availability of support services such as childcare, their pay, benefits and conditions of work, the insecurity of their jobs or enterprises, their access to vocational training.

Almost two-thirds of employed women in developing countries are in vulnerable jobs, as own-account or unpaid family workers, as casual agricultural labourers at the bottom of a global value chain, as workers in urban factories and workshops or as domestic servants. It provided on-the-job training and stipends for women with children so that

REFERENCES

- Jhamtani, Rural women: The powerless partners in development, *Kurukshetra*, 43(8) (1995), 61-63. A. Tejaswini and S. Veerabhadraiah, Knowledge assessment of rural women on DWCRA and their problems, *Kurukshetra*, 51(4) (1996), 46-47.
- A.R. Desai and A. Mohiuddin, Involving women in agriculture – Issues and strategies, *India Journal of Rural Development*, 11(5) (1992), 506-648.
- G.T. Govindappa, Rural women entrepreneurship- Constraints and strategies, *Kurukshetra*, 48(2) (1999), 11-14.
- K.S. Jyothi, Employment pattern and empowerment of rural women – A study in Kolar district, M. Sc. (Agri.) Thesis, (1998), University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore.
- N. Nikhade and A. Patwardhan, Economic contribution of home-makers through household production, *Maharashtra Journal of Extension Education*, 9(1990), 81-86.
- R. Parekh and K. Mehta, Empowerment of rural women – A case study of Udwada, Proceedings of the National Consultation on Gender Issues in Credit in the Rural Non-Farm Sector, 14-15 September (1992), Organized by SNTD Women's University, Bombay.
- S. Giriappa, Women empowerment and decision making analysis in rural enterprises, Paper Presented at International Conference on Gender Equity through Women's Empowerment, 23-29 December (1997), Lucknow.
- Srisankari and K. Uma, Women's participation in agriculture, *Kurukshetra*, 43(8) (1995), 103104. Thangamuthu and N. Manimekalai, Generation of employment for women through DWCRA, *Journal of Rural Development*, 8(4) (1989), 431-438.

A SOCIOLOGICAL STUDY ON CHILD ABUSE

Dr. R. Rajendran

Assistant Professor, Sociology Wing DDE,
Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar

Delegation to the 2nd International Women's Rights Assembly
(Regd: 04IWRA2)

INTRODUCTION

Child abuse is a violation of the basic human rights of a child and is an outcome of a set of inter-related familial, social, psychological and economic factors. The problem of child abuse and human rights violations is one of the most critical matters on the international human rights agenda. In the Indian context, acceptance of child rights as primary inviolable rights is fairly recent, as is the universal understanding of it.

Definition of child abuse

Physical Abuse: Physical abuse is the inflicting of physical injury upon a child. This may include burning, hitting, punching, shaking, kicking, beating or otherwise harming a child. The parent or caretaker may not have intended to hurt the child. It may, however, be the result of over-discipline or physical punishment that is inappropriate to the child's age.

Sexual Abuse: Sexual abuse is inappropriate sexual behavior with a child. It includes fondling a child's genitals, making the child fondle the adult's genitals, intercourse, incest, rape, sodomy, exhibitionism and sexual exploitation.

Emotional Abuse: Emotional abuse is also known as verbal abuse, mental abuse, and psychological maltreatment. It includes acts or the failures to act by parents or caretakers that have caused or could cause, serious behavioral, cognitive, emotional, or mental trauma.

Sexual abuse is unwanted sexual activity, with perpetrators using force, making threats or taking advantage of victims not able to give consent. Most victims and perpetrators know each other. Immediate reactions to sexual abuse include shock, fear or disbelief. Long-term symptoms include anxiety, fear or post-traumatic stress disorder. While efforts to treat sex offenders remain unpromising, psychological interventions for survivors — especially group therapy — appears effective.

Health and Physical Consequences

- Pregnancy, especially in early adolescence
- Sexually transmitted diseases
- Difficulty walking, sitting, or standing
- Torn, stained, or bloody underclothing
- Vaginal/penile discharge
- Pain during urination or urinary tract infections
- Bruises on the child's mouth, to the hard or soft palate
- Sleep disturbances (difficulty sleeping, nightmares)

- Enuresis & Self-injurious behavior (cutting, burning oneself, suicide attempts)

Preventing Sexual Abuse

- Know the signs and symptoms of sexual abuse so that you might recognize a child who is being harmed.
- Be willing to report suspicions. Remember, it is not your job to prove that sexual abuse has occurred, and your report might keep a child from further harm Offer ongoing communication about sexual touching and other topics to create trusting relationships with children.
- Teach children self-protection skills that they have the right to say no or stop and to tell an adult and keep telling the adult until they are believed.
- Support community and school programs to prevent abuse

Objectives

- To understand the socio demographic profile of the respondents.
- To understand the adolescent girls knowledge regarding sexual abuse.
- To understand the attitude of adolescent girls towards sexual abuse.
- To understand the practices adopted by the respondents to handle the sexually abusive situation & reasons for not responding in sexual abuse situation.

Sampling

The researcher selected adolescent girls studying in both government and unaided schools in kaveripattinam Block as the universe of study. The researcher selected total 60 adolescent girls from both government school and private school for comparative study. A descriptive research design was adopted for the present study. Simple random sampling method is used in this research work because the study conducted in a homogeneous group. All the elements in the population have an equal chance of being selected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Distribution of respondents by age.

Age	Unaided school		Government	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
12	0	0	4	13.3
13	9	30.0	19	63.3
14	13	43.3	5	16.7
15	8	26.7	2	6.7
Total	30	100.0	30	100.0

Most of the respondents are in the group of 12-15 years. The above table shows that 30 percent of respondents in unaided school are belong to the age group of 13 years while in government school 63.3 percent respondents belong to the group of 13 years. Very few of (6.7 percent) respondents in government school are belongs the age group of 15 years while in unaided school 26.7 percent of respondents belongs to the age group of 15 years of age.

Distribution of the respondents of the basis of class

Name of the class	Unaided school		Government school	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
8 th standard	10	33.3	17	56.7
9 th standard	20	66.7	13	43.3
Total	30	100.0	30	100.0

From the above table it is clear that the majority of the respondents in unaided school are from 9th standard while in government school the majority respondents from 8th standard.

Distribution Of family members of the respondents

Name of the family members	Unaided school		Government school	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
1	0	0	1	3.3
2	0	0	0	0
3	4	13.3	0	0
4	14	46.7	2	6.7
5	4	13.3	9	30.0
6	4	13.3	6	20.0
7	0	0	5	16.7
8	0	0	7	23.3
9	4	13.3	0	0
Total	30	100.0	30	100

From the table it is clear that most of the respondents in the government school are from big families. Whereas, most of the respondents in the private school are from small family.

Knowledge Level

SI NO	Statement	yes		No		Don't know	
		US	GS	US	GS	US	GS
1	Friendly with your parents	30 100%	29 96.7%	0 0%	1 3.3%	0 0%	0 0%
2	Own a mobile phone	1 3.3%	2 6.7%	29 96.7%	28 93.3%	0 0%	0 0%
3	A member in any kind of social network	3 10.0%	0 0%	27 90.0%	30 100%	0 0%	0 0%
4	Heard the word 'sexual abuse'	30 100%	21 70%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	9 30.0%
5	A problem only for girls	4 13.3%	13 43.3%	14 46.7%	0 0%	12 40.0%	17 56.7%
6	Sex related comments included in sexual abuse	16 53.3%	11 36.7%	3 10.0%	0 0%	11 36.7%	19 63.3%
7	Sex related messages/phone calls are not a sexual abuse	7 23.3%	12 40.0%	12 40.0%	2 6.7%	11 36.7%	16 53.3%
8	Physical abuse is the real abuse	16 53.3%	13 43.3%	5 16.7%	2 6.7%	9 30.0%	15 50.0%
9	Exhibitionism is a sexual abuse?	8 26.7%	14 46.7%	5 16.7%	0 0%	17 56.7%	16 53.3%
10	Rape is the cruelest sexual abuse	26 86.7%	26 86.7%	1 3.3%	0 0%	3 10.0%	4 13.3%
11	Way of dressing of girls leads to sexual abuse	21 70.0%	19 63.3%	9 30.0%	3 10.0%	0 0%	8 26.7%
12	Sexual abuse happens only from unfamiliar person	0 0%	3 10.0%	28 93.3%	16 53.3%	2 6.7%	11 36.7%
13	Sexual abuse happens within the family	17 56.7%	22 73.3%	3 10.0%	1 3.3%	10 33.3%	7 23.3%

Friendly with your parents: Cent percent of the respondents in unaided school are friendly with their parents as compared to the respondents in government school.

Own a mobile phone: The 6.7 percent respondents in government school have their own mobile phones. **A member in any kind of social network:** In government school there are not single respondents the member in any kind of social networks, while 10.0 percent of respondents in unaided school are the members in social network. **Heard the word 'sexual abuse':** cent percent of the respondents in unaided school are heard the word 'sexual abuse' while in government school only 70 percent of respondents heard about the word 'sexual abuse'. Rest 30 percent didn't heard about the word sexual abuse.

A problem only for girl: 43.3 percent of respondents in government school revealed that the problem of sexual abuse is the problem only for girls. Sex related comments included in sexual abuse : Sexual abuse may include verbal remarks like name calling, sex related comments, sex related messages, phone calls, exhibiting sex organs, sex related films, pictures etc. These abuses create mental stress and strain to a person. Majority (53.3percent) of respondents in unaided school has average knowledge, 10 percent have low knowledge and 36.7 percent have moderate knowledge about the mental abuse. While in government school majority (63.3percent) of respondents has moderate knowledge, 36.7 percent have average knowledge about the mental abuse.

Sex related messages / phone calls are not a sexual abuse : Sexual abuse may include verbal remarks like name calling, sex related comments, sex related messages, phone calls, exhibiting sex organs, sex related films, pictures etc. These abuses create mental stress and strain to a person. The statement is to understand the knowledge of the respondents regarding mental abuse. Majority (40 percent) of the respondents in unaided school had more knowledge about the mental abuse while compared to the respondents in government school. **Physical abuse is the real abuse :** sexual abuse can be physical abuse like unwanted touching, sexual kissing ,fondling, forced sexual behavior, rape etc. 50 percent of respondents in government school stated that they do not know about the physical abuse, while in unaided school 53 percent of the respondents had knowledge regarding the physical abuse.

Exhibitionism is sexual abuse: 56.7 percent of respondents in unaided school didn't know whether exhibitionism is a sexual abuse. While in government school 46.7 percent respondents respond to the statement. Majority (86.7percent) of the respondents in both government and unaided school respectively had the same knowledge regarding the rape. So 70.0 percent respondents in unaided school do not know that the dressing of the girls leads to sexual abuse. While in government school 63.3 percent respondents.

Sexual abuse happens only from unfamiliar person: Sexual abuse happens within the family also. Here 73.3 percent respondents in government school are agreeing with this statement.

Attitude Level

SI No	Statement	Strongly agree		Agree		Disagree		No response	
		US	GS	US	GS	US	GS	US	GS
1	Careless of the girls is the main reason of sexual abuse	3 10.0%	8 26.7%	17 56.7%	6 20.0%	1 3.3%	3 10.0%	0 0%	8 26.7%
2	People will keep a negative attitude towards a sexual abused girl	16 53.3%	8 26.7%	13 43.3%	5 16.7%	0 0%	9 30.0%	0 0%	6 20.0%
3	Even though a girl is aware about the abuse, she is not responding to the authority	20 66.7%	7 23.3%	10 33.3%	6 20.0%	0 0%	4 13.3%	0 0%	11 36.7%
4	Travelling alone is not reason for sexual abuse	6 20.0%	12 40.0%	16 53.3%	4 13.3%	7 23.3%	1 3.3%	1 3.3%	0 0%
5	It is very risk to run behind the police procedures	10 33.3%	5 16.7%	10 33.3%	1 3.3%	1 3.3%	8 26.7%	5 16.7%	8 26.7%
6	I am not sure that my family will support me	3 10.0%	7 23.3%	0 0%	6 20.0%	21 70.0%	2 6.7%	2 6.7%	8 26.7%
7	Abused girls will be voiceless	7 23.3%	15 50.0%	11 36.7%	3 10.0%	2 6.7%	3 10.0%	1 3.3%	8 26.7%
8	It is better to keep silence because girls are not physically strong to react towards boys	0 0%	10 33.3%	3 10.0%	1 3.3%	15 50.0%	4 13.3%	0 0%	9 30.0%
9	Abused girl will hate the presence of boys in future	5 16.7%	11 36.7%	0 0%	12 40.0%	3 10.0%	2 6.7%	10 33.3%	5 16.7%

Girl's carelessness is the main reason of sexual abuse: in this statement majority of the respondents in unaided school (56.7 percent) agreed with the statement and 30.0 percent respondents disagreed with the statement. In case of the government school 26.7 percent of the respondents are strongly agree with the statement and very few respondents (26.7 percent) in government school had no response with this statement. In case of the respondents in unaided school 56.7 percent are strongly agreeing & 43.3 percent are just agreeing the statement. Only 3.3 percent of the respondents are disagreeing this statement. While in case of the respondents in government school 30.3 percent of the respondents are strongly disagreeing this statement.

While compare to the respondents in government school 66.7 percent of the respondents in unaided school are strongly agreeing with this statement. None of them are disagreeing with this statement. But in case of the respondents in government school 36.7 percent are not responding and 13.3 percent are strongly disagreeing with this statement.

Travelling alone is not a reason for sexual abuse: 40.0 percent & 13.3 percent of the respondents in the government school are strongly agreeing and agreeing with this statement & 43.3 percent are disagreeing with this statement. But in case of unaided school 53.3 percent are agreeing with this statement and 23.3 percent are strongly disagreeing with this statement. It is a very risk to run behind the police procedures: While compared to unaided school majority of the respondents (26.7 percent) in government school are disagreeing and strongly disagreeing with this statement. But comparing to the government school in case of the unaided school 33.3 percent of the respondent are strongly agreeing and agreeing with this statement. I am not sure that my family will support me: compared to government school respondent's majorities (70.0 percent) of the respondents in the unaided school are strongly disagreeing with this statement & only 10.3 percent are strongly agreeing with this statement. Abused girls will be voiceless: 50 percent & 23.3 percent of the respondents in the government school & unaided school are strongly agreeing with this statement. 30.3 percent and 3.3 percent of the respondents in the unaided school and government school are disagreeing with this statement. 26.7 percent of the respondents in the government school are not responding to this statement.

It is better to keep silence because girls are not physically strong to react towards boys: 33.3 percent of respondents of the government school are strongly agreeing with this statement. 40 percent and 50 percent of the respondents in the unaided school are disagreeing and strongly disagreeing with this statement. 30 percent of the respondents in government school are not responding with this statement. Abused girls will hate the presence boys in future: 36.7 percent and 40.0 percent of the respondent in government school are strongly agreeing with this statement. 40.7 percent and 16.7 percent of the respondents in the unaided school are disagreeing and strongly disagreeing with this statement. In case of both government school and unaided school respondents 16.7 percent and 33.3 percent are not responding for this statement.

A SOCIOLOGICAL STUDY ON CHILD ABUSE

Dr. R. Rajendran

The Rights, Vol-III: Issue-I

8th, March, 2017

ISSN: 2454-9096 (online)

Practice level

Si No	Statement	yes		No		Don't know	
		US	GS	US	GS	US	GS
1	I will keep away from him if somebody trying to abuse me	29 96.7%	21 70.0%	0 0%	1 3.3%	1 3.3%	8 26.7%
2	I will tolerate without any reaction or pretend like not knowing	2 6.7%	3 10.0%	27 90.0%	16 53.3%	1 3.3%	11 36.7%
3	I will try to frighten the abusing person	18 60.0%	9 30.0%	2 6.7%	8 26.7%	10 33.3%	13 43.3%
4	I will appeal to the authority or co-travelers	27 90.0%	21 70%	2 6.7%	1 3.3%	1 3.3%	8 26.7%
5	I will react in a way to draw the attention of others	15 50.0%	9 30.0%	4 13.3%	1 3.3%	11 36.7%	20 66.7%
6	Keep the help number of helpline, women cell etc	16 53.3%	16 53.3%	12 40.0%	4 13.3%	2 6.7%	10 33.3%
7	Feel that what others will think about me	23 76.7%	18 60.0%	4 13.3%	9 30.0%	3 10.0%	3 10.0%
8	Feeling whether surrounding people support me if I react	9 30.0%	6 20.0%	16 53.3%	11 36.7%	5 16.7%	13 43.3%
9	Fear about being a social issue in the media if I seek police help	23 76.7%	18 60.0%	4 13.3%	9 30.0%	3 10.0%	3 10.0%
10	Afraid that the abusing person will take revenge if I threat	9 30.0%	6 20.0%	16 53.3%	11 36.7%	5 16.7%	13 43.3%
11	Society may consider me guilt	15 50.0%	14 46.7%	5 16.7%	3 10.0%	10 33.3%	13 43.3%
12	It may affect my marriage proposals in future	21 70.0%	12 40.0%	3 10.0%	5 16.7%	6 20.0%	13 43.3%
13	I will make friendship with co-travelers to avoid fear	24 80.0%	19 63.3%	4 13.3%	3 10.0%	2 6.7%	8 26.7%

NB:-US- Unaided school, GS-Government School.

I will keep away from him if somebody trying to abuse me: 96.7 percent of the respondent in unaided school and 70.0 percent of the respondent in the government school are agreeing with this statement. 3.3 percent & 26.7 percent of the respondent in both in unaided school and government school are said that they don't know about this statement.

I will tolerate without any reaction or pretend like not knowing: 90.0 percent and 53.3 percent of the respondents in both unaided and government school are disagreeing with this statement. Compared to the unaided school 3.3 percent of the respondents in the government schools are agreeing with this statement.

I will try to frighten the abusing person: 60.0 percent & 30.0 percent of the respondents in both unaided school and government school are agreeing with this statement. 43.4 percent and 43.3 percent of the respondents in the unaided school and government school don't know about this statement. I will appeal to the authority or co-travelers: 90.0 percent and 70.0 percent of the respondent in unaided school and government school are agreeing with this statement. 26.7 percent of the respondent in government school doesn't know about this statement. I will react in a way to draw the attention of others: 50.0 percent & 30.0 percent of the respondent in unaided school and government school are agreeing with this statement. 36.7 percent and 66.7 percent of the respondents in both unaided school and government school don't know about this statement.

Feeling whether surrounding people support me if I react: Majority (53.3 percent) of the respondents in both unaided school and the government school are agreeing with this statement. 40.0 percent of the respondent unaided school and 13.3 percent of the respondents in government school are agreeing with this statement. Fear about being a social issue in the media if I seek police help: 76.7 percent and 60.0 percent of the respondents in unaided school and government school are agreeing with this statement. 10.0 percent respondents in both school are don't know what the statement is.

Afraid that the abusing person will take revenge if I threat: 53.3 percent and 36.7 percent of the respondents in the unaided school are disagreeing with this statement. 43.3 percent respondents in the government school don't know about this statement. Society may consider me guilt: 50.0 percent of the respondents in both unaided school and government school are agreeing with this statement. 33.3 percent and 43.3 percent of respondents in both schools don't know about this. It may affect my marriage proposals in future: 70 percent & 40.0 percent of the respondents in the unaided school & government school are agreeing with this statement. 20.0 percent and 43.3 percent of the respondents in both schools don't know about this statement.

CONCLUSION

The researcher understood that the respondent I government school have very low level of knowledge and attitude towards sexual abuse as compared to the respondents in unaided school due to social set up, family background economic status etc. To provide awareness about sexual abuse. The Sex education and value education should be including in school curriculum. To strengthen the school counseling programs. To Self defense classes also included in school curriculum. The Students need to be trained in seeking the help of various helpline services like child line, women cell, and police station.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Books:

- Sotirios, Sarantakos, (1998) Social research, Mac Millan Press Ltd Lal Das d., Principles of Social Research
- Hurlock, Elizaeth, (1981) Development of Psychology A Life Span Approach, 5th Edition, Tata Mc. Grawhill publishing company.
- Janssen.D., Growing Up Sexually. Volume 2. The Sexual Curriculum. O. led. Victoria Park, W.A. Books Reborn.
- Khan., (1998) Sexual Physical Abuse: A Threat To Reproductive And Sexual health exchange.

Journals:

- Raajneeshsharma, August 2005, Prevention of Sexual Harrasment, – Social welfare
- Deepak Borses, July 2009, Questions About Sex Ask To Your Friend Social welfare.
- Radha Krishna Rao, January 2010 A New Front Child Abuse – Social welfare
- Shivani Khandekar December 2010 Do Girls Recognize Sexual abuse - Social welfare
- V.B. Bhata March 1998, Violence Against Women A Social disease Social welfare
- Dr, Ujwala Hiremath May 1998, Campus Survey On Sexual abuse - Social welfare
- Anupriya Mallic December 2004, Child Sexual Abuse Facts And Facts - Social welfare

Website

- Wikipedia. Org/ wiki/child abuse
- wcd.nic.in/ sexual abuse